

PROTOTYPE OF NEW PROCESSED FOOD PRODUCTS

D5.14

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Short Description
<p>This documentation forms the basis for the realization of the project prototypes of new food products. Together with the prototype objectives, general considerations and recommendations, it provides a scientific-technological description of the R&I process carried out to realize the prototypes as result of the testing phase in lab / at small-scale level (WP4) and feedback gathered from the in-field validation (WP5). According to the impact pathway approach, it describes the conducted activities, the reached outputs and outcomes, and the obtained measures of main key performance indicators demonstrating the impact. The detailed functional and nutritional properties of the validated prototypes are reported in D5.16</p>

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Table of Contents

1. General introduction	8
2. Prototypes for different new food products.....	10
2.1. Olive oil	10
2.1.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	10
2.1.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	10
2.1.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	10
2.1.4 Summary of the outputs.....	12
2.2. Nutrient enriched baked snacks containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans	15
2.2.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	15
2.2.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	15
2.2.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	16
2.2.4 Summary of the outputs.....	17
2.2.5 Conclusions.....	19
2.3. Cookies made from wheat and legume-based composite flours	20
2.3.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	20
2.3.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	21
2.3.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	22
2.3.4 Summary of the outputs.....	23
2.3.5 Conclusions.....	26
2.4. Energetic bars made from wheat flasks and dried fruits	27
2.4.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	27
2.4.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	27
2.4.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	28
2.4.4 Summary of the outputs.....	29
2.4.5 Conclusions.....	32

2.5. Fish cakes, crackers, nuggets, fillets and balls	33
2.5.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	33
2.5.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	33
2.5.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	33
2.5.4 Summary of the outputs.....	35
2.5.5 Conclusions.....	38
2.6. Cereal-based snack for children (quinoa snack for children – <i>Mandazi</i>) ..	40
2.6.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	40
2.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	41
2.6.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	42
2.6.4 Summary of the outputs.....	49
2.6.5 Conclusions.....	56
2.7. Therapeutic food (tamarillo juice, for adults with diabetes).....	57
2.7.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	57
2.7.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	58
2.7.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	58
2.7.4 Summary of the outputs.....	60
2.7.5 Conclusions.....	76
2.8. Prototype for bean sauce	77
2.8.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	77
2.8.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	77
2.8.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	78
2.8.4 Summary of the outputs.....	79
2.8.5 Conclusions.....	81
2.9. Wheat flour enriched with grain amaranth flour	83
2.9.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	83
2.9.2 Prerequisites for the prototype.....	83
2.9.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	84

2.9.4 Summary of the outputs.....	85
2.9.5 Conclusions.....	86
2.10. Noodles from orange fleshed sweet potatoes and bio-fortified beans (partially substituting wheat)	87
2.10.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	87
2.10.2 Prerequisites for the prototype	87
2.10.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	88
2.10.4 Summary of the outputs.....	89
2.10.5 Conclusions	91
2.11. Fish oil.....	92
2.11.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives.....	92
2.11.2 Prerequisites for the prototype	92
2.11.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating.....	92
2.11.4 Summary of the outputs.....	93
2.11.5 Conclusions	95
3. Overall conclusion.....	97

Abbreviations and glossary

Abbreviation / specialist term	Explanation
DIR	Beni Mellal
FOO	Flavored olive oil
GIE	Economic Interest Group
KE	Kenya
KEBS	Kenya Bureau of Standards
KEPC	Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Limited
MA	Morocco
NCD	Non-Communicable Diseases
Nectar	Fruit drink a minimum level of whole fruit juices as a key ingredient
OFSP	Orange fleshed sweet potatoes
PGO	DIR Beni Mellal
RSM	Response surface methodology
RTS	Ready-to-Serve
SD	Standard Deviation
SPME-GC-MS	Solid-phase microextraction followed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry
Tamarillo	Tree tomato is also known as tamarillo; the names used interchangeably
TN	Tunisia
TVC	Total Viable Count of microorganisms
TZ	Tanzania
UG	Uganda
WF	Wheat flakes
DA	Dried apricots
DP	Dried peach
DM	Dried melon
F	Formulation
NGO	Nongovernmental Organization
GDA	Agricultural Development Groups

1. General introduction

Limited dietary diversity is a contributing factor to malnutrition. FoodLAND sought to support nutrition performance improvement in selected Food Hubs by promoting agricultural biodiversity and food diversity. Development and promotion of new food products was adopted as one of the strategies towards improving nutrition. Hence a number of new food products (listed in Table 1 below) were developed through technological research.

Table 1: List of new food products developed and their targeted Food Hubs

Food Hub	New food product
Zoyout Dir Beni Mellal (MA)	Virgin and/or extra virgin olive oil Flavored olive oils
Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Orange-fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and bio-fortified beans
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Cookies: Wheat; legumes (<i>pea / faba bean / chickpea</i>)
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Energetic bars: wheat flasks; dried fruits (<i>apricot, peach, melon</i>)
Kitui (KE)	Cereal-based snack for children (quinoa snack for children)
Mukurweini (KE)	Tamarillo juice, for adults with diabetes
Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Bean sauce
Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Amaranth-enriched wheat
Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Noodles from orange fleshed sweet potatoes and bio-fortified beans (partially substituting wheat)
Masaka/Kajjasi (UG)	Fish oil
Masaka/Kajjasi (UG)	Fish cakes, crackers, balls, noodles, nuggets, sausages, and burgers

The foods listed in Table 1 were mainly developed from the new ingredients reported on in D5.11 by applying a variety of secondary processing tools

described in D5.12. The selection of ingredients and processing methods was aimed at obtaining nutrient and nutraceutical rich food products, with potential to contribute to addressing nutrition gaps reported in D2.5, including protein-energy malnutrition, micro-nutrient deficiency, and low intake of foods with healthy promoting components. The food products were also meant to contribute to realisation of nutritional recommendations reported in D2.6, most of which address the needs for the nutritionally vulnerable population groups, including infants, young children, women of reproductive age and the elderly. The development of new foods by FoodLAND is on the backdrop of increasing consumption of processed foods in Africa, yet most of the processed foods on the market are of low nutritional value. The low nutritional value of most processed foods is attributable to the use low nutritional value ingredients and processing methods that lead to over refinement of raw materials. In addition to nutritional and nutraceutical value, new processed foods were designed to confer other advantages, including convenience, shelf-stability, safety, and desirable sensory properties.

Details of prototypes for the different developed new food products follow. The description includes follows the impact pathway approach (Figure 1). It thus highlights the activities undertaken, the outputs, outcomes and impacts anticipated, both to direct project beneficiaries (primary impact) and on cross-cutting aspects (secondary impact).

Figure 1: Impact pathway

2. Prototypes for different new food products

2.1. Olive oil

2.1.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Olive oil is a high value healthy product and is an important commodity in Tunisia and Morocco. The quality of olive oil depends on the quality of olives and on the production process applied. The aim of technological research conducted by FoodLAND on olive oil was to find an appropriate and sustainable technological processes that can be used to obtain high-quality, more stable (less prone to fermentative and oxidative defects) and globally marketable virgin olive oils, including flavoured oils.

2.1.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for development of the prototype are given below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Availability of raw materials	M
2	Availability of flavoring materials	1
3	Availability of mills	1
4	Processing skills development for SME staff	1
5	Products certification	1
6	Storage facilities necessary to store raw materials and finished goods under suitable conditions.	1
7	Transportation and logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.1.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Vegetable products and spices widely used in Mediterranean diet, e.g. orange, pomegranate, black pepper and ginger powder were added during the olive milling process to transfer peculiar sensory and compositional characteristics. Moreover, in view of sustainability, the pulp as well as by-products (e.g. peel, pomace) were used.

In this sense, to promote the innovation of these operative phases, flavoured olive oil (FOO) has been produced at lab scale (UNIBO) with commercial freeze-dried powders, added during the malaxation phase, made of orange by-product and ginger to find the best ratio of olive oil to flavoring powder. The optimized option has been replicated at semi-industrial scale (UNIBO) and at industrial scale (GIE, ENAM).

UNIBO carried out trials with both lab-scale and semi-industrial scale mill producing flavoured olive oils (FOO) with a commercial powder made of freeze-dried orange pomace (by-product) and with freeze-dried ginger at lab-scale.

ENAM carried out experiments with industrial scale mill producing flavoured olive oils (FOO). The crushed olives consisted exclusively of the "Picholine Marocaine" variety obtained from the DIR Beni Mellal (PGO). These were crushed in the industrial unit of the GIE (Economic Interest Group) "DIR Beni Mellal". This is a modern, continuous two-phase unit with a maximum processing capacity of 60 tonnes per day.

The processes tested consisted of the following steps:

Co-malaxation at lab-scale test (Abencor® system) A ratio of 1 kg of olives to 10 g of flavoring powder (orange by-product powder or ginger powder) was used. The flavoring powder (orange by-product or ginger) was added directly to olive paste during the malaxation phase. The powder had to be stored in closed container to avoid direct contact with the air.

Co-malaxation at industrial scale (two-phase decanter as centrifugation system) A ration of 1:100 was used at industrial level. For the two flavoring materials, the quantities used were 80 kg of olives + 800 g of orange by-product powder and 100 kg of olives + 1 kg of ginger powder. These ratios of olives to flavoring materials (orange and ginger powder) have been shared with the partners (ENAM, GIE) in order to produce in Morocco the same kind of oil at industrial scale.

Ginger flour (ginger just dried and grinded) was added to olive paste of Moroccan Picholine during malaxation at 1% but also at 1.5% and 2%. The optimized ratio between olives and ginger powder has been shared with the partners (ENAM, GIE) in order to produce in Morocco the same kind of oil tested

by UNIBO. The flavoured olive oil (FOO) and its control sample (CS, 0% ginger) produced at industrial level were shipped to Italy at time 0 (T0, just produced) and after 3 months of storage at room temperature (T3) analysed to determine volatile compounds and the sensory quality.

2.1.4 Summary of the outputs

2.1.4.1 Results and achievements

The olive oil produced at lab scale with orange powder had low free acidity (0.1%). Volatile profile analysis (SPME-GC-MS) revealed presence of typical compounds of orange such as D-Limonene, β -cis-ocimene and geranyl nitrile. Other compounds related to positive attributes of olive oil (*trans*-2-hexanal, hexanal, 2-penten-1-ol) were also detected.

Sensory evaluation by a trained panel revealed no defect. The oil was characterized as fruity 1.8, bitter 1.7 and pungent 1.0 (plus secondary note resembling orange).

The olive oil flavored with ginger powder, on the other hand, had no perceived defects for oils flavored with 1%, 1.2%, 1.5% and 2% ginger. Trained panelists characterised ginger flavored oils as fruity (plus secondary notes resembling ginger, balsamic resinous, citrus), bitter and pungent, with levels varying with level of ginger added.

Volatile profile was coherent with the result of the sensory analysis, indeed volatile compounds responsible for specific sensory attributes, related to the flavouring matrix, were detected. For example, volatile compounds related to the balsamic perceived attribute, such as eucalyptol, showed increasing concentration coherent with the percentage ginger powder added to olives. The same happened for other volatile compounds such as β -pinene and zingiberene. Other volatile compounds specific for the ginger flavour were detected, such as (+)-4-carene. In addition, compounds responsible for citrus attributes were detected mainly in the sample with higher olives/ginger powder ratio (2%) in line with sensory analysis results: geraniol, geranial and β -citral. Volatile compounds responsible for positive attributes in olive oil were detected in comparable concentration among samples, even if the sensory perception may have been

influenced and masked by the ginger flavour: hexanol (and its isomers) and hexanal (and its isomers).

The shelf-life study focused mainly on the changes in fruity-, oxidation- and fermentation-related compounds over time in ginger-flavored oils. Eighteen key compounds were selected based on their oxidative, fermentative, or fruity attributes, as well as their association with ginger-derived components. The study found that oxidation-derived 2-nonanol and fermentation-related 2-heptanone were initially present in ginger-flavored oils, probably due to the lack of oil filtration, increasing with ginger concentration but disappearing after three months, likely due to ginger's antioxidant properties. Overall, the three-month storage period led to an increase in some volatile compounds associated with fermentation, suggesting a metabolic activity in the product. However, fruity notes remained stable, indicating that the storage process did not negatively affect the formation of positive aromatic compounds.

2.1.4.2 Relevant production

- Poster “Flavored olive oils by co-milling of olives, black pepper and orange fruits pomace: compositional characterization, sensory properties and sustainability aspects”. Authors: Celeste Lazzarini, Alessandra Bendini, Enrico Valli, Nouredine Mokhtari, Koutar Elfazazi, Tullia Gallina Toschi, Susan Nchimbi Msolla, Marco Setti.
- Presentation to the Italian Congress SISSG 2022 “Oli e grassi alimentari: innovazione e sostenibilità nella produzione e nel controllo”, Perugia (PG), Italy, 15th-17th June 2022. Poster “Production, Composition and Sensory Characterization of New Flavoured Oils: Focus on Sustainability”. Author: Celeste Lazzarini. Presented to the 27^o Workshop on the Developments in the Italian PhD Research on food Science, Technology and Biotechnology, Portici (NA), Italy, 13th-15th Sept. 2023.
- Scientific article “Characterization of New Flavored Oils obtained through the Co-Milling of Olives and Vegetable Food Products”. Authors: Celeste Lazzarini, Matilde Tura, Mara Mandrioli, Marco Setti, Nouredine Mokhtari, Abdelaziz Ait Elkassia, Sara Barbieri, Enrico Valli, Alessandra Bendini and Tullia Gallina Toschi. *Foods* **2025**, *14*, 687.

2.1.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Dir Beni Mellal (MA)	Flavoured olive oil (FOO)	5 Cooperatives (30 farmers)

2.1.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Dir Beni Mellal (MA)	Flavoured olive oil (FOO)	<p>Amelioration of compositional, functional and nutritional properties of olive oil:</p> <p>10% increased of healthy and sensory properties</p> <p>15% increase of income</p> <p>10% reduction of food losses</p> <p>Increase in diversity of oil accessible by consumers</p>

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.1.5 Conclusions

Besides the positive effects on health by improving the quality of olive oil in general, this prototype is anticipated to improve the diversity of olive oil products on offer by flavouring and stimulating market demand for these specific products. The introduction of these new products should have a positive impact on the income levels of small farmers compared with conventional products, which have a lower profit margin (no market segmentation).

2.2. Nutrient enriched baked snacks containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans

2.2.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Many ready to eat snacks available in Uganda are low in nutritional value and do not address the nutritional problems of under-nutrition, micro-nutrient deficiency and obesity, which are widely spread in these countries (as reported in D2.5). A number of nutrient and nutraceutical rich food raw materials and ingredients have been identified but their use in production of processed foods is limited. Technological research evaluated the use of composite flour constituted of orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans to partially substitute wheat in the production of baked doughnuts, commonly referred to as *daddies*, in Uganda.

Refined wheat flour, which is the main ingredient typically used in baking is generally low in proteins, micronutrients and fibre. Baked doughnuts made from refined wheat are therefore low in nutritional value. By blending wheat flour with more nutritious ingredients like legumes and biofortified tubers, it is possible to produce nutrient enhanced baked snacks. The properties of such snacks as well as their acceptability are influenced by the formulations used. Studies are therefore needed before any formulations can be promoted among food operators. Technology development activities on baked doughnuts were aimed at determining the optimal formulation for making baked doughnuts, with partial substitution of wheat with a composite flour consisting of OFSP, grain amaranth and biofortified beans.

A description of the research and innovation process carried out to address the aforementioned need, the prerequisites, the participants and the results (based on impact pathway) follows.

2.2.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for the realisation of the protocol are outlined in the table below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Availability of appropriate processing equipment and facilities	M
2	Processing skills development for SME staff	1
3	Availability of quality raw materials in sufficient volumes	1
4	Connection to electricity and water supply	1
5	Products certification	1
11	Access to suitable packaging materials and equipment	2
12	Storage facilities necessary to store raw materials and finished goods under suitable conditions.	1
18	Transportation and logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.2.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Baked doughnuts (commonly referred to as *daddies* in Uganda) were made using 40% non-instant flour constituted of orange fleshed sweet potatoes (OFSP), grain amaranth and biofortified beans flour and 60% wheat. The composite flour used was made from an RSM optimised formulation and consisted of 37.8% OFSP, 32.2% biofortified beans and 30% grain amaranth. Properties of flour used and the optimisation process are reported in D 5.11. Other ingredients used were wheat flour, sugar, eggs and butter. For every 100 kg of flour, 25 kg of sugar, 25 kg of margarine, 10 eggs, 500 g of baking flour were used. Vanilla essence (0.2%), carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) (0.1%), and water (8%) were also used. The ingredients were kneaded into a dough. The dough was then shaped into *daddies* (cuboid shape) form (5.0 x 5.0 cm) and baked in an electric oven at 150°C for 55 minutes. *Daddies* were removed from the oven and allowed to cool at ambient temperature for about 10 minutes, packed in polyethylene bags for subsequent analyses. The doughnuts were subjected to proximate composition analysis and sensory evaluation.

2.2.4 Summary of the outputs

2.2.4.1 Results and achievements

Snacks produced contained relatively high levels of protein and fibre (Table 2.2.1) compared to snacks made from only refined wheat. This can be attributed to the relatively high nutritional value of the composite flour used to replace wheat. The snack is generally high in fat, which makes it a high energy product, that's suitable for very active individuals such as school-age children. These snacks (*daddies*) are commonly consumed by children in boarding schools. These are unlikely to have a problem with excessive energy intake. The high energy content of the snack is therefore not likely to lead to overweight and obesity.

The snacks' sensory scores (Table 2.2.2) for all attributes were relatively high (≥ 7.8 on a 9 point scale). This shows that the product was well accepted by panelists. This is indicative of high potential for market acceptability.

Table 2.2.1. Nutritional composition of baked snacks with wheat partially substituted with orange-fleshed based composite flour

Water	Protein	Ash	Fibre	Fat	Carbohydrates	β carotene	Iron	Zinc
3.81±0.11	18.72±0.38	1.88±0.05	1.77±0.06	20.23±0.16	52.59±1.68	0.548±0.056	0.892±0.028	0.493±0.024

n=3

Table 2.2.2 Sensory evaluation of baked snacks with wheat partially substituted with orange-fleshed based composite flour

Appearance	Taste	Overall acceptability
7.8±1.4	7.9±1.3	8.4±1.1

n= 35

2.2.4.2 Relevant production

Exploring new ingredients for nutritional enhancement of processed foods. Oral presentation at the 2024 International Journal Forum on Interdisciplinary Food Science (Food Bioscience & Food Nutrition) joint with the 16th ISNFF Conference and Exhibition. December 2024. Wuxi, China.

2.2.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kamuli-Kalerwe (UG)	Nutrient enhanced baked doughnuts containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans	1 SME

2.2.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kamuli-Kalerwe (UG)	Nutrient enhanced baked doughnuts containing orange fleshed sweet potatoes, grain amaranth and biofortified beans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhanced SME capacity in value addition ● Business opportunity for SME ● Improved access of consumers to nutrient rich products ● Increased farmer access to market for agricultural produce

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.2.5 Conclusions

Technological research has shown that doughnuts made with partial substitution (40%) of wheat with composite flour constituting OFSP, grain amaranth and biofortified beans, contain markedly higher levels of protein, fibre and micronutrients compared to those made wholly from wheat. The doughnuts were found to be acceptable by sensory panelists. Substitution of wheat only doughnuts with the developed snacks would therefore lead to nutritional advantages. If commercialised and widely consumed, the developed doughnuts have potential to contribute to improved nutrition in Uganda, especially among children and youth who tend to snack often. For successful commercialisation of the prototype, availability of the new ingredients used (OFSP and biofortified beans flour) is required, as these are currently not available commercially. Hence there is need for investment in production of these flours. Products certification is another prerequisite for commercial exploitation of the developed snacks and this requires action by processing businesses and the national food certification body (Uganda National Bureau of Standards). The prototype has been disseminated to Nutreal Ltd, a FoodLAND SME partner to consider commercialisation.

2.3. Cookies made from wheat and legume-based composite flours

2.3.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

This prototype on cookies made from wheat and legume-based composite flours (pea, faba bean, and chickpea) is designed to address key nutritional, social, and economic challenges. A primary issue it seeks to tackle is malnutrition, particularly protein-energy deficiency, which is prevalent among vulnerable groups such as children. By incorporating legumes, the prototype aims to enhance the nutritional quality of conventional snacks, providing higher protein content, essential amino acids, and dietary fiber compared to standard wheat-based cookies. From a societal perspective, the product addresses the growing demand for affordable, nutritious, and sustainable food options. Legumes, being a low-cost and environmentally friendly protein source, contribute to sustainability and food security goals. The concept also supports diet diversification, encouraging the inclusion of plant-based protein in everyday diets. The prototype combines innovative food formulation with sustainable practices to deliver a snack that is both nutritious and appealing. The use of composite flours from wheat and legumes ensures an optimal balance of taste, texture, and nutrient density, making the cookies an ideal choice for both children and adults. Enhancing the nutritional profile of snacks by integrating protein-rich legume flours. The product aims also to promote sustainable agriculture by encouraging the use of legumes, which improve soil fertility and reduce environmental impact. Additionally, the product aims to empower women in the food value chain, creating opportunities for female entrepreneurs in production, distribution, and marketing. By addressing these intertwined nutritional and social challenges, the snack prototype contributes to healthier communities, equitable access to nutritious foods, and sustainable dietary habits.

A description of the research and innovation process carried out to develop wheat-legume cookies, including the prerequisites, the participants and the results (based on impact pathway) follows.

2.3.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for the realisation of the protocol are outlined in the table below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Flour Milling Equipment not mandatory if pre-milled untreated and germinated faba bean flour is sourced	M
2	Soaking Tanks/Containers for faba beans soaking	M
3	Sprouting Trays/Racks for faba beans germination	M
4	Water Spraying System to Main bean moisture during sprouting	1
5	Controlled Environment Chamber for optimal germination conditions	1
6	Dryer for germinated faba bean	M
7	Mixing Machine ensures uniform mixing of ingredients, critical for quality and consistency	M
8	Dough Sheeter and Cutter facilitate efficient shaping and uniformity of cookies. Can be replaced with manual rolling/cutting	1
9	Baking Oven core equipment for baking cookies.	M
10	Cooling Rack essential to ensure moisture evaporation post-baking and maintain cookie quality.	1
11	Packaging Equipment required to maintain product freshness and extend shelf life. Manual packaging can be an alternative.	1
12	Storage Facilities necessary to store raw materials and finished goods under suitable conditions.	M
13	Costs: Inputs and Raw Materials: Wheat Flour, Faba Bean Flour (Untreated and Germinated), Sugar, Vegetable Oil, eggs, milk powder, Baking Powder, Salt Equipment acquisition Facility setup and maintenance: Includes costs for space, utilities, and safety compliance. Labor costs: Salaries for personnel involved in production and quality assurance.	M
14	Production Facilities: A clean, food-safe environment with sufficient space for milling, blending, packaging.	M
15	Storage Units: Temperature- and humidity-controlled storage areas for raw materials (wheat, faba beans) and finished products (cookies) to prevent spoilage and maintain quality.	1

16	Utilities: Reliable electricity supply for operating equipment. Access to clean water for sanitation and maintenance.	M
17	Adequate ventilation systems for a safe working environment.	M
18	Transportation and Logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
19	Waste Management Systems: Facilities for handling and disposing of by-products or waste materials in an eco-friendly manner.	2
20	Safety and Compliance Infrastructure: Fire safety systems, first aid kits, and emergency exits for worker safety.	1
* <i>Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low</i>		

2.3.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

The development of cookies was based on different composite flour formulations using wheat (90, 85 and 80%) and untreated microwave heated and germinated legumes (faba bean, pea and chickpea) added at mixture levels of 10, 15 and 20%. The supplemented ingredients were eggs, vegetable fat, sugar, milk powder, salt and baking powder. Different cookies were subjected to nutritional and physical and sensory analysis. Based on the obtained results and the legumes price the cookies made by untreated or germinated faba bean at 20% was selected for the validation. Validated product was subjected to the same characterization analysis (Figure 2.3.1).

Figure 2.3.1. Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating of snacks (cookies based on wheat legumes composite flour), FB: faba bean; P: Pea; CP: chickpea; MP: milk

powder; VF: vegetable fat; BP: baking powder; UFBB: untreated faba bean flour and GBBF: germinated faba bean flour

2.3.4 Summary of the outputs

2.3.4.1 Results and achievements

The results demonstrated that the cookie formulations significantly influenced their nutritional, physical, and sensory properties. The highest phenolic content and antioxidant activity were observed in cookies containing untreated and germinated faba bean and pea. Pea supplementation also had an impact on the colour of the cookies. Additionally, texture parameters were affected by the inclusion of legumes. The prototype validation confirmed the nutritional improvements achieved with untreated or germinated faba bean. Overall, the product

2.3.4.2 Relevant production

Scientific article under finalization and to be submitted in 2025: Formulation and evaluation of untreated and germinated legume-enriched cookies: a mixture design study on quality and antioxidant activity.

2.3.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Snacks (cookies based on wheat and faba bean flour)	Farmers (4) SMEs (2) NGOs: GDA Kharroub Enfidha (12 operators) GDA Chebika (15 operators)

2.3.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Snacks (cookies based on wheat and faba bean flour)	<p>Technology :</p> <p>KPI definition: KPI1: partnership extension index (PEI) (measures partnership growth and success, collaboration between the different stakeholders in the value chain:</p> <p>-PEI = 6/10. The collaboration among the various stakeholders was satisfactory but requires further effort to ensure the sustainability of the partnership. Governmental organizations play a vital role in strengthening relationships between stakeholders</p> <p>KPI2: sustainability score (SS) (measures the environmental and socio economic impacts).</p> <p>-SS =7/10: this score is given since the ingredients are sourced sustainably and locally. Faba beans are nitrogen-fixing legumes, meaning they improve soil fertility and reduce the need for synthetic fertilizers, which lowers greenhouse gas emissions.</p>

		<p>They are a sustainable source of protein and help diversify crop rotations, contributing to improved soil health and reduced pest pressures.</p> <p>Substituting a portion of wheat with faba bean flour can reduce reliance on monoculture wheat farming, which has a higher environmental footprint. Promoting faba beans in value-added products can boost demand for this crop, increasing income for farmers and promoting agricultural resilience.</p> <p>Nutritional:</p> <p>KPI definition: KPI1: Ingredient quality index (IQI) (used to measure the global quality of ingredients included in the product)</p> <p>-IQI=9/10: this score is based on quality analysis results, an improvement in nutritional properties was recorded with the maintaining of physical quality aspects</p> <p>KPI2: customer satisfaction assessment (CSA) (measures the level of consumer satisfaction)</p>
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		-CSA=7/10: 69% of consumers rated the wheat-faba bean cookies above 6/10, compared to only 40% for the control cookies.
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The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.3.5 Conclusions

The wheat and faba bean cookie prototype has the potential to significantly address nutritional gaps, particularly in protein, antioxidant and fiber intake, while catering to the growing demand for healthy, plant-based snacks. To ensure its success, it is recommended to strengthen collaborations with health organizations and schools, streamline the supply chain for consistent raw material quality, and scale production efficiently. Expanding production capacity and exploring packaging innovations will be crucial for broader market reach. Technological improvements, such as process automation and ingredient optimization, are necessary to enhance production efficiency and product quality. Additionally, ongoing research and consumer insights will help refine the product and ensure its market competitiveness. The product has potential to impact public health policies, create local employment, and support the agricultural economy. To maintain growth and relevance, continued investment in R&I will be key to enhancing the nutritional profile and exploring new product variations.

2.4. Energetic bars made from wheat flasks and dried fruits

2.4.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

The energetic bars made from wheat flakes and dried fruits are designed to provide a convenient, nutritious, and appealing snack option specifically tailored to meet the dietary needs of children. This open prototype aims to address common challenges such as poor eating habits, the prevalence of unhealthy processed snacks, and the lack of time parents often face in preparing balanced meals for their kids. By combining wholesome ingredients like wheat flakes and dried fruits, the bars offer a rich source of energy, fiber, and essential vitamins, ensuring they are both tasty and beneficial for children's growth and development. The concept prioritizes affordability, accessibility, and eco-friendliness, targeting parents, schools, and caregivers who seek healthier snacks. Specific objectives include reducing children's consumption of processed foods, promoting balanced nutrition, and supporting local agriculture through the use of regionally sourced ingredients. Additionally, the prototype considers gender inclusivity by ensuring the product meets the nutritional needs of all children, while also creating opportunities for women in production and distribution, thereby addressing economic disparities and fostering community development.

2.4.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Baking Oven core equipment for wheat flakes preparation	M
2	Cutting and Shaping Machines for energetic bars preparation	1
3	Mixing machine: ensures uniform mixing of ingredients, critical for quality and consistency	1
4	Dryer for fruit and wheat flakes drying	M
5	Packaging Equipment required to maintain product freshness and extend shelf life. Manual packaging can be an alternative.	1
6	Flaking machine is used to process whole wheat grains into flakes, the machine typically uses rollers to flatten boiled wheat.	2
7	Storage Facilities necessary to store raw materials and finished goods under suitable conditions.	M

8	Costs: Inputs and Raw Materials: wheat, fruits, glucose syrup or honey Equipment acquisition Facility setup and maintenance: Includes costs for space, utilities, and safety compliance. Labour costs: Salaries for personnel involved in production and quality assurance.	M
9	Production Facilities: A clean, food-safe environment with sufficient space for drying, grinding of fruits and wheat flakes preparation and energetic bars preparation and packaging.	M
10	Utilities: Reliable electricity supply for operating equipment. Access to clean water for sanitation and maintenance.	M
11	Adequate ventilation systems for a safe working environment.	M
12	Transportation and Logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
13	Waste Management Systems: Facilities for handling and disposing of by-products or waste materials in an eco-friendly manner.	1
14	Safety and Compliance Infrastructure: Fire safety systems, first aid kits, and emergency exits for worker safety.	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.4.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

The development of the energetic bars followed a rigorous scientific-technological approach, grounded in research and innovation (R&I) to ensure optimal nutritional value, taste, and texture. The R&I path involved three key stages: development, testing, and validation. During the development phase, three distinct formulations were created, each with varying percentages of dried fruits (apricot, peach, and melon) and wheat flakes, both of which were selected due to their high production levels in the Enfidha/Chebika Food Hub, ensuring local sourcing and sustainability. Glucose syrup was added to balance energy content, sweetness, and binding properties. The testing phase focused on evaluating these formulations based on criteria such as nutritional composition, sensory appeal, shelf stability, and ease of production. Validation was conducted by analyzing the testing results, which revealed that the formulation with the highest percentage of dried fruits delivered superior nutritional benefits. This formulation was selected as the final product, aligning with the goal of creating a healthy, appealing, and innovative snack for children while supporting local agriculture (Figure 2.41). The process underscores the importance of iterative

testing, user-centered design, and regional resource utilization in achieving a successful and impactful product.

Figure 2.4.1 - Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating of snacks (energetic bars with wheat and dried fruits (apricot, peach and melon), WF(wheat flakes), DA (dried apricots), DP (dried peach), DM (dried melon), GS (glucose syrup) F (formulation).

2.4.4 Summary of the outputs

2.4.4.1 Results and achievements

The results obtained during the testing phase indicated that the percentage of fruit used in the formulation significantly influenced both the nutritional and physical properties of the energetic bars. A higher level of fruit supplementation led to an increase in total phenols and flavonoids, which in turn enhanced the antioxidant activity of the product. These findings were further confirmed by the validation assays, which demonstrated consistency in the nutritional and sensory attributes. Notably, the product maintained its desirable qualities, ensuring a balanced nutritional profile while also offering an appealing taste and texture. Consumer feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with the energetic bars.

2.4.4.2 Relevant production

Master Graduation project report was produced entitled " Opportunities for Establishing an Apricot Drying Unit"

Article can be published on the developed energetic bar product: "Developing a Nutritious and Convenient Snack: The Energetic Bars with Wheat Flakes and Dried Fruits".

2.4.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new technology / system/ tool / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Snacks (energetic bars with wheat flakes and dried fruits (apricot, peach and melon))	Farmers (5) SMEs(1) NGOs: GDA Kharroub Enfidha (12 operators) GDA Chebika (15 operators)

2.4.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Enfidha/Chebika (TN)	Snacks (energetic bars with wheat flakes and dried fruits (apricot, peach and melon))	Technology : KPI definition: KPI1: partnership extension index (PEI) (measures partnership growth and success, collaboration between the different stakeholders in the value chain: -PEI = 6/10. The collaboration among the various stakeholders was satisfactory but requires further effort to ensure the sustainability of the partnership. Governmental organizations play a vital role in strengthening relationships between stakeholders

		<p>KPI2: sustainability score (SS) (measures the environmental and socio economic impacts).</p> <p>-SS =8/10: this score is given since the production of energetic bars made from wheat flakes and dried fruits, apricot, peach, and melon, offers significant environmental and socio-economic benefits. Environmentally, it promotes the efficient use of fruits that might otherwise go to waste, especially surplus or imperfect produce, thereby reducing food waste and its associated environmental impacts. The use of dried fruits also extends the shelf life of seasonal produce, ensuring year-round availability. Socio-economically, the product supports local agriculture by creating a market for wheat and fruits, boosting farmers' incomes and encouraging sustainable farming practices. Additionally, the small-scale production model can empower local communities, providing income opportunities.</p> <p>Nutritional:</p> <p>KPI definition: KPI1: Ingredient quality index (IQI) ((used to measure the global quality of ingredients included in the product)</p> <p>-IQI=8/10: this score is based on quality analysis results, the product boasts remarkable nutritional properties, particularly its high antioxidant activity, which plays a crucial role in promoting overall health. This feature is primarily attributed to the rich concentration of bioactive compounds found in the dried fruits, such as apricots, peaches, and melons. Additionally, the inclusion of wheat flakes contributes essential dietary fiber and energy,</p>
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		<p>making the bars not only a delicious snack but also a functional food that supports children's growth, immunity, and long-term well-being.</p> <p>KPI2: customer satisfaction assessment (CSA) (measures the level of consumer satisfaction)</p> <p>-CSA=7/10: 90% of consumers rated the energetic bars above 6/10 for overall acceptance while 60% gave them a score below 5/10 for the acid taste</p>
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The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND novel food products).

2.4.5 Conclusions

The development and validation of the energetic bars made with wheat flakes and dried fruits highlight a promising innovation in the realm of healthy, sustainable, and locally sourced snacks for children. From an organizational perspective, the product supports the Enfidha/Chebika food hub by utilizing locally abundant ingredients, fostering regional economic growth, and creating opportunities for women in production and distribution. Operationally, the selected formulation with the highest percentage of dried fruits ensures a balance between nutritional value, taste, and texture, making it appealing to children while meeting parental expectations for health and convenience. Policy-wise, this initiative aligns with broader goals of promoting sustainable agriculture, reducing reliance on processed foods, and addressing nutritional gaps in children's diets. Recommendations include scaling up production through partnerships with schools and local markets, conducting long-term studies to assess the product's impact on children's health, to enhance marketability. Additionally, raising awareness about the benefits of locally sourced, nutrient-rich snacks could drive consumer demand and encourage similar innovations. Overall, this product not only addresses immediate nutritional needs but also sets a precedent for integrating sustainability, health, and community development into food innovation.

2.5. Fish cakes, crackers, nuggets, fillets and balls

2.5.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Traditionally, the most common preservation methods for fish are smoking, drying and salting. However, secondary fish products such as fish balls, fish crackers and fish nuggets provide higher value and can be processed from raw materials such as mince from fish carcasses. Also extruded (squeezed through heating process) ready to eat snacks can be processed using micronutrient dense fish bone powder as a base. As part of FoodLAND activities to promote food and dietary diversity in Masaka/Kajjansi food hub, these products were developed from farmed fish species of tilapia, *Barbus* and catfish.

2.5.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

The prerequisites for developing and implementing the protocol are listed below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Raw materials: Quality fish mince from GHP (Good Hygienic Practices) processing, Proximity to raw material source – e.g. fish processing facility	1
2	Equipment: Deep fryer, Oven	1
3	Others: Potable water, knives, cooking oil, rolling pin, cutter, spices,	1 - 2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.5.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

The mince from the carcass was the primary raw material used to develop the secondary products however, where insufficient, the fillet was also minced. An electric mincer was used to produce mice from carcass and fillet.

The processing technologies used to develop the products included deep frying (battered & breaded products – fish balls, nuggets and crackers), and extrusion – fish bone-maize snack.

The fish balls were prepared according to Duman and Peksezer (2016). Fish balls were composed of 64% fish mince and 36% other ingredients, including: 18% wheat flour, 11.4% onions, 1.8% bread crumbs, 3.8% fat, 0.7% salt and 0.26% black pepper. All the ingredients were mixed together to form a uniform dough. This basic mixture was processed to form small (25 g) balls which were deep fried using vegetable oil (Roki). Deep frying was done at 200 °C for approximately 15 minutes (till golden brown). Excess oil was drained from the fish balls on a paper towel and then allowed to cool.

The fish nuggets were prepared according to methods by Moosavi Nasab et al. (2019) with slight modification. The fish nuggets contained fish mince (80.24%), water (9.95%), lemon (0.30%), onion (6.01%), spices (0.36%), wheat flour (1.90%), and sugar (0.2%). All ingredients were mixed to form a dough. The nuggets were made into star shapes using a cutter, coated with bread crumbs and deep fried with vegetable oil (Roki) at 200 °C for 15 minutes. Excess oil was drained using paper towel and the nuggets allowed to cool.

The crackers were made by following the method by Zzaman et al. (2017) with slight modification. Crackers were made by mixing 200 g fish mince, 180 g tapioca starch, 12 g sugar, 13.5 g salt, 30.5 g ice, 3 g MSG, and 2.1 g sodium bicarbonate. The dough was made into cylindrical shapes with 4.3 cm diameter and steamed at 90°C for 30 minutes (until firm) followed by chilling in a refrigerator (4 °C) for approximately 1 hour. They were cut into 2 mm thick pieces which were oven dried at 50°C for 12 hours. They were deep fried in hot vegetable oil (Roki) for 30 seconds.

Extruded fish bone-maize snack was prepared with fish powder from bones of tilapia and catfish. Maize grits were ground to pass through 200 µm sieve using laboratory mill. Several preliminary trials were made to select the mixing ratio of fish flour incorporation in maize flour. The fish bone flour was mixed with the maize flour in the ratio of 1:2 in the ribbon blender for 15 min to ensure uniform mixing. This ratio was found to be ideal after preliminary trials showed that a higher fish bone flour ratio resulted in clogging of the extruder due to high fat content of the carcasses. Salt and dried spices of choice (in powder form) were added at 2% into the mixture and again blended for 10 min. The mixture was introduced in the extruder hopper and extruded (Model no. THEX-100, Sejin, South Korea) at 150 °C, speed at 1450 rpm and cutting speed 350 rpm.

2.5.4 Summary of the outputs

2.5.4.1 Results and achievements

Figure 2.5.1

Table 2.5.1 Proximate composition of fish products

Products/Nutrient composition (%)	Crude Protein	Crude Fat	Dry Matter Content	Ash
Soft smoked fish fillets	79.4±0.2	5.8±0.2	94.9±0.9	5.0±0.4
Fish snacks (extruded)	11.9±0.1	5.5±0.0	96.3±0.7	5.1±0.2
Fish fingers	36.6±0.2	28.7±0.3	92.4±0.4	2.6±0.0
Fish nuggets	15.3±0.8	13.9±0.4	53.1±1.5	3.3±0.2
Fish balls	14.3±0.2	14.4±1.4	57.1±1.8	1.9±0.4
Fish cakes	20.2±0.2	5.9±0.1	63.3±3.7	1.7±1.5
Fish crackers	14.9±0.4	18.4±0.4	97.4±0.1	3.1±0.2
Fish burgers	17.2±0.4	16.9±0.2	66.6±0.5	3.4±0.4

In the analysed samples the soft smoked fish fillet had the highest protein content approximately 80% and the least observed in extruded fish snacks approximately 12%. For crude fat, the fish fingers had the highest at 28.7% and lowest in extruded fish snacks (5.5%). Dry matter content was highest in extruded fish snack 97.4% and lowest in the fish nuggets (53.1%). Ash content was highest in extruded fish snack (5.1%) and lowest in the fish cakes (1.7%).

Sensory evaluation during validation

During the validation exercise 30 individuals were trained in production of fish balls, fish cakes, fish fingers, fish nuggets and extruded fish bone snacks. Ten of the trainees also evaluated the products for sensory acceptance using a 9 point hedonic scale. Results from the sensory evaluation (Figure 2.5.2) indicate that fish nuggets were the most acceptable product (8.6).

Figure 2.5.2. Sensory evaluation of the products during the validation exercise

2.5.4.2 Relevant production

Masette M., Akullo D., Tinyiro S. E. and Aruho C (2023). Development of secondary products from farmed fish. FoodLAND Annual meeting, Zanzibar, January 2023.

2.5.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	fish cakes and crackers fish fillets, balls, noodles, nuggets, sausages, and burgers	30 farmers/2 SMEs

2.5.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	<i>fish cakes and crackers fish fillets, balls, noodles, nuggets, sausages, and burgers</i>	<i>Increased protein and micronutrient intake by Food Hub members Increased diversity of snacks in Food Hubs Increased revenue from fish by farmers</i>

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.5.5 Conclusions

The results above demonstrate the potential of innovative processing of fish and fish by-products in increasing food diversity. The products made from fish were convenient, highly nutritious and acceptable to consumers. Commercial production of the diverse food products developed can benefit fish farmers, SMEs (processors/traders) and fish consumers. To realise the potential benefits, there is need for food actors such as food processing SMEs or caterers to adopt this prototype. Communication activities throughout the remaining part of the project will continue to disseminate the prototypes to potential users, with a view of promoting adoption.

References

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Moosavi-Nasab, M., Asgari, F., & Oliyaei, N. (2019). Quality evaluation of surimi and fish nuggets from Queen fish (*Scomberoides commersonianus*). *Food science & nutrition*, 7(10), 3206-3215.

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2.6. Cereal-based snack for children (quinoa snack for children – *Mandazi*)

2.6.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Malnutrition in Kenya remains a serious health problem that requires sustainable interventions to resolve. Among children, wasting and iron deficiency are the main forms of malnutrition that compromise growth, development and survival (WHO, 2012). In Kenya, 22% of children aged 6 – 59 months are iron deficient while 13.3% have iron deficiency anaemia (MoH, 2011). Approximately 35% of children between the ages of 12 – 23 months are iron deficient in Kenya. There is no significant difference in the prevalence of iron deficiency between children living in rural (22%) and urban (23%) areas (MoH, 2011).

In Kenya, four percent of children under the age of five years are wasted (KNBS, 2015). Wasting undermines children’s physical and mental growth and thus impairs motor and cognitive development. This compromises a child’s learning ability and school performance (WHO, 2012). In addition, wasting compromises a child’s immune system increasing the frequency, severity and duration of infections and thus increasing the risk of childhood death (WHO, 2012).

Quinoa has recently drawn attention as a food that can have significant impact on nutrition status of populations including children due to its high nutritional value. Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa* Willd) is a plant that belongs to the family Amaranthaceae, commonly known as the amaranth family (Toapanta et al., 2016). This family also includes other plants such as spinach and *mchicha* (*terere*) both of which are eaten as vegetables in Kenya. The amaranth family contains approximately 2500 species that are typically herbaceous plants distributed all over the world. Due to its high nutritive value and tolerance to drought and salinity, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) designated quinoa as one of the crops that will provide food security in the 21st century (Alvarez-Jubete et al., 2010). Quinoa contains a perfect balance of all essential amino acids and its protein value is comparable to that of casein in milk (Vega-Galvez et al., 2010). Quinoa is rich in iron and has been documented to have health benefits among populations with iron-deficiency anaemia.

The quinoa plant can grow in arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs) as it is tolerant to drought (Alvarez-Jubete et al., 2010). As such, quinoa offers a significant contribution to resolving malnutrition and food insecurity especially with the predictions of declined rainfall and extended drought periods in future. Quinoa can grow in high-salinity soils which makes it ideal to grow in marginalized regions. In addition the quinoa grain has high shelf-life stability with a high endurance of low storage temperatures, low gelling point and high resistance to retrogradation (Navruz-Varli, 2016). This makes the grain ideal for processing and new product development of foods with a creamy and smooth texture. No studies have been conducted to investigate whether developing a quinoa enriched food product may be beneficial to the growth and development of school-aged children.

The main objective of the R&I activities on quinoa was to determine the effectiveness of a quinoa-enriched new food product in improving the nutrition status of children aged two to six years. The specific objectives were to:

1. To develop a quinoa-wheat composite flour for a deep fried snack (*mandazi*) for preschool-aged children;
2. To assess acceptance of the mandazi production technology;
3. To analyse economic feasibility of the commercial production of the composite flour; and
4. To determine the effect of the deep fried snack (*mandazi*) in improving the nutritional status of preschool-aged children (aged 2-6 years).

A description of the research and innovation process carried out to develop quinoa enriched new food product, including the prerequisites, the participants and the results (based on impact pathway) follows.

2.6.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Below are the prerequisites for production of quinoa enriched new food product.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Hammer mill (US\$ 1,016)</i>	M
2	<i>Flour mixer (US\$ 5,000)</i>	M

3	Flour filling, packing machine (US\$ 10,000)	M
4	Building (US\$ 15,750)	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.6.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

For prototype development, quinoa seeds were procured from Kenya (Healthy U LTD) then grown at The University of Nairobi College of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences. This was then used to scale up by growing the quinoa plant in Kitui County, however, serious drought and lack of irrigation led to failure of the crop. Finally, for the purposes of this study, the quinoa used for this study was “White Quinoa” procured from Healthy U LTD in Nairobi. A total of 150 kg of white Quinoa was purchased for product development and feeding trials. The Quinoa Enriched New Food product (QENFP) formulated and developed were mandazi snacks for school going children at the level of early Education programme in Kitui County. Snack production was done at the Department of Food Science, Nutrition and Technology, University of Nairobi food chemistry laboratory. The products were then subjected to tests to determine their nutrient composition, sensory properties and shelf life stability.

The study was conducted in three phases: a consumer survey, prototype development and an effectiveness study of the QENFP on study children.

Prototype development and evaluation of market acceptability

Wheat flour and quinoa seeds were stored in dry plastic bags at the University of Nairobi, Food Chemistry laboratory. The quinoa seeds were manually cleaned to remove foreign matter and damaged or immature seeds. Initially, BioBio and Titicaca varieties of quinoa was procured and multiplied within University of Nairobi farm and seeds shared with farmers in Kitui County. This two varieties were marred with two challenges: i) Poor weather/drought in Kitui that lead to desiccation of the crops in the farmers field. Only one farmer was able to harvest a few grams in the agroecological zones of Kitui; ii) These were bitter varieties and the prototype even with the least amount of quinoa was not palatable.

To resolve the problem of quinoa bitterness, quinoa flour was prepared according to the method of Vilche et al. (2003) with some modifications to remove

saponins which negatively affect the taste and digestibility of quinoa (Navruz-Varli, 2016). After manual cleaning, the quinoa seeds were washed twice with cold water then hand scrubbed with alkaline water for 10 – 20 minutes and rinsed with 1% citric acid solution for 10 minutes to remove saponins. Saponin content was then be checked by placing the seeds in a tube, adding water and vigorously shaking for 30 seconds. If no foaming occurred, it was assumed that all saponins has been removed (El-Sohaimy et al., 2019). If foaming occurred, the saponin removal procedure was repeated. Saponin-free seeds were oven-dried overnight at 45±1°C. The seeds were spread in a thin layer in the oven tray to avoid germination and any contamination. Finally, the quinoa seeds were ground into flour using a hammer mill (KARIZMA- JX-1000A) and stored at 5°C (Vilche et al., 2003). Even with this, the mandazi were not palatable. Then non-bitter variety of quinoa (White Quinoa) was procured, prototype developed and sensory tests done. This was then followed with comprehensive evaluation of market acceptability using biometric tests using facial expressions. The prototypes were formulated by varying ratios of wheat and white quinoa as follows.

Ratios of wheat flour and quinoa flour were blended in ratios shown in Table 2.6.1.

Table 2.6.1: Blending ratios for wheat and quinoa flour in the three developed flours

	Ratio of Quinoa			
	34%	44%	54%	70%
Quinoa flour (g)	34	44	54	70
Wheat glour (g)	66	56	46	30
Salt (g)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Sugar (g)	11.5	11.5	11.5	11.5
Water (ml)	55	55	55	55
Ghee (g)	10	10	10	10
Baking podwer (g)	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8
Yeast (g)	1	1	1	1

Dough and mandazi processing was as described in the Kenyan Food Recipes (FAO/GOK 2018). However, ghee was used for dough formation instead of utilization of a shortening. The prototype with 70% quinoa was selected for further analysis as it had the highest energy content; the analysis involved

sensory and market acceptability, shelf-life, stakeholders technology acceptability, and mandazi school snack efficacy study.

Milling of quinoa grains

Quinoa was procured as grains (Figure 2.6.1). The grains were milled using hammer mills at the Kitui Food Hub at the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Ltd (KEPC) (Figure 2.6.2). The fine flour strainer of the hammer was used for milling the quinoa grains. The milling was repeated 3 rounds to get a fine texture needed for preparation of mandazi. One round milling would be needed for flour used for porridge.

Plate1: Picture quinoa grains

Plate 2: Mill used for milling quinoa (at KEPC)

Recipe of preparation of quinoa *mandazi* snacks

The dry ingredients were first mixed (quinoa flour, wheat flour, sugar, salt, and baking powder and yeast). Then ghee was added and mixed with the dry ingredients until the dough mixture appeared buttered and granule-like. Warm water (30-40 degrees Celsius) was added sequentially in small amounts with kneading the dough while removing dough stuck in the hands. The dough is not exactly as that of wheat (100%), since it has low plasticity – molding can still be performed. After kneading, the dough was matured by covering with a wet cloth for about 45 minutes. The dough was then reworked for about 1 minute and then divided into 240 grams dough balls. The dough batches (balls) were then flattened like a pizza bread – and divided into 4 equal part which were in the triangle shape (mandazi shape). The cut dough in mandazi shape was then deep-fried using palm oil under medium heat for 2 minutes, then put in a metallic bucket for cooling. Each of the prototypes was subjected to sensory evaluation, and laboratory testing for proximate nutrient composition (Results are presented in Table 2.6.1). The prototype with 70% was used to produce mandazi for further studies together with the control (100% wheat).

Plate 3. Dough that has been cut into 240 g

Plate 4. Uniform size of mandazi shaped dough before deep frying

Plate 6. Ready to eat mandazi

Plate 5. A child snacking a mandazi

The *mandazi* was analysed for proximate composition, amino acids profile, iron content and sensory acceptance (using 7 point hedonic rating). In addition to conventional sensory evaluation, eye tracking tests were used to measure and analyse emotional responses.

Shelf life evaluation of mandazi snacks

Deep fried mandazi snacks were stored at room temperature for 5 days and monitored for moisture content, free fatty acids, peroxide value, yeast and molds. The mandazis were stored in three packaging materials: Kraft paper bags, gunny bags and PET plastic containers. The foods were analysed pre-storage and monitored every day in storage for changes in: fat acidity, peroxide value, moisture content and growth of yeasts and moulds.

Fat acidity was measured as the milligrams of potassium hydroxide required to neutralize the free acid in a one-gram sample of the flour. Peroxide value was determined by mixing a gram of the flour sample in a solution of potassium iodide and acetic acid followed by titration with a solution of sodium thiosulphate and starch. Moisture content was determined through drying in an air oven at 105°C and weighing of the residue (AOAC, 2005). Yeasts and moulds was enumerated as the total viable counts (TVCs) through the streak-plate technique (ISO, 2001).

Plate 7: Mandazi packaged in different packaging material – Clear paper is new biodegradable packaging (top); Aluminum coated (middle), kraft paper laminated (bottom)

Evaluation of technology acceptance

The technology for preparation of quinoa mandazi snacks was evaluated for acceptance by administering a questionnaire consisting of 8 questions with a seven likert scale (7 Extremely likely, 6 quite likely, 5 slightly likely, 4 neither likely or unlikely, 3 slightly unlikely, 2 quite unlikely, 1 Extremely unlikely). The technology acceptance questionnaire was filled by 39 participants from Kitui Food Hub.

Plate 8: Stakeholders involved in technology acceptance evaluation

Evaluation of effectiveness of quinoa mandazi snacks on nutritional quality of children in early education programs in Kitui County.

A short interventional study was conducted in Kitui County, in two schools in the East Sub-County. The study recruited 160 children attending preschool classes in two school in Kitui East Sub-county. The study was conducted in the month of September and October 2024 for a duration of 1 month. The total number of school children recruited that consumed the mandazi snacks for the entire study period were 160. However, due to incomplete data for the two rounds of data collection – i.e. before and after feeding school children with the mandazi snacks the final number of children data collected were from School A – intervention (33), School B- control (41). Children in the intervention school were fed with 60 g of quinoa mandazi snack while children in the control school received 60 g of wheat mandazi snack for 3 weeks. The children were dewormed one week before feeding with mandazi snacks was started. Data collection involved assessment of anthropometric measurements and assessment of dietary quality of children and nutrient intake. Data was collected from 64 children in the control school (School B) and 49 of the intervention school (School A); however, study participants dropped from the study due to incomplete data were 31 and 8 from the intervention (School A) and control (School B) schools.

Plate 9: Children enjoying mandazi snack at school

Plate 10. Post sample collection treatment: 20% sulphuric acid was added to urine samples immediately after collection to prevent escape of ammonia. Both urine and stool pairs were tied together and samples frozen until analysis of nitrogen content.

2.6.4 Summary of the outputs

2.6.4.1 Results and achievements

Composition of 4 prototypes formulated by optimizing quantity of quinoa in mandazi snacks

The energy content for the four prototypes developed was in the range 386.26 - 451.3 Kcal/100 g (Table 2.6.2). The prototype with the highest quinoa quantity was selected. This also had the highest energy content.

Proximate composition of quinoa (composite flour 70%) and 30% Wheat flour and mandazi snacks prepared using the composite flour

The 70% quinoa and 30% wheat flour deep fried snack (mandazi) for children prepared in the laboratory had 19.75±1.19% moisture, 28.34±0.02% fat, 1.27±0.11% fibre, 2.88±0.02% ash, 8.04±0.04% protein, 39.72±1.31% carbohydrates,

446.12±5.2 kcal/100 g energy, 106.78±0.005 ppm calcium, 31.87±0.005 ppm zinc and 62.20±0.005 ppm iron. This is the UoN prototype arising from the optimisation of the quantity of quinoa. It had the highest energy content.

The composite flour was also prepared at the industrial scale at the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Limited (KEPC) factory in the Kitui Food Hub. The moisture content of quinoa flour used for mandazi preparation was 5.32±0.19% while that of the mandazi was 15.1±.69%. Fat content of the composite flour was 1.28±0.05% while that of the mandazi was 18.28±0.04%. The energy per 100 g of composite flour 371.64±1.13 kcal while that of the mandazi was 414.4±2.29 kcal. The protein content was 13.11±0.59% and 5.63±0.32% for flour and mandazi, respectively. The differences with the laboratory results can be attributed to the inaccuracy of the weight measurements at the industrial scale.

Shelf-life of quinoa flour and *mandazi*

Deep fried mandazi snacks were stored at room temperature for 5 days and monitored for moisture content, free fatty acids, peroxide value, yeast and molds. The effect of packaging materials on the moisture content of quinoa snacks during the shelf-life study is shown in Figure 2.6.1. The moisture content of the samples increased with increase in storage period for each of the packaging materials with the highest recorded in the biofilm with an increase of 29.76% and lowest in the laminated Kraft paper with an increase of 14.59%. The results indicated that continuing the study beyond 5 days was not necessary due to the high moisture content.

Figure 2.6.1: Moisture content of mandazi snacks stored in different packaging; metallized pouch, unlaminated kraft paper, Laminated kraft paper, and new bio-based packaging

The effect of packaging materials on the FFA (free fatty acid-oleic acid) of quinoa snacks during the shelf-life study is shown in Figure 2.6.2. The FFA of the samples increased with increase in storage period for each of the packaging materials with the highest recorded in the biofilm with a value of 0.68 ± 0.02 and lowest in the laminated Kraft paper with a value of 0.4 ± 0.016 .

Figure 2.6.2: Free fatty acids content of mandazi snacks stored in different packaging; metalized pouch, unlaminated kraft paper, Laminated kraft paper, and new bio-based packaging

The results of peroxide value were zero for the 5 days the product was under study showing no oxidation present and therefore the product remained fresh.

From the results there was significant difference ($p < 0.005$) between changes in moisture and free fatty acids content for samples packaged in different the packaging materials.

From the microbiological results there was no growth of indicator organisms (coliforms), yeasts and molds and therefore the product was microbiologically stable. This could be attributed to the good hygiene practices, deep frying of the quinoa snacks which destroyed any microbes present and due to the relatively low moisture content of the snacks.

Efficacy trials

A longitudinal study to test the efficacy of the composite flour *mandazi* on the nutritional status (MUAC and wasteline) of pre-school children in Kitui Food Hub found that the difference between the intervention and the control groups was significant only for height ($p \leq 0.05$), and not for MUAC and wasteline ($p > 0.05$). A longer feeding trial period would perhaps yield a different result. The adoption of the technology of preparing quinoa *mandazi* snacks was scored highly with all the criteria ranking 'extremely likely' to 'quite likely' to adopt the technology.

Technology acceptance or validation

The technology for quinoa *mandazi* manufacture was show-cased and ready to eat products tasted by various stakeholders meeting organized by FoodLAND in Kitui County. The products were rated highly with an indication of likelihood of adoption (Table 2.6.2). Among the respondents 56% (n=22) were male while 43% (n=17) were female. The adoption of the technology of preparing quinoa *mandazi* snacks was scored highly with all the criteria ranking 'extremely likely' to 'quite likely' to adopt the technology. The panelists were from the following age groups <30 yrs (6%), 30-39 yrs (24%), 40-49 yrs (26%), 50-60 yrs (18%) and >60 yrs were 29% of the study participants.

Table 2.6.2: Evaluation of participants acceptance of quinoa based *mandazi* snacks technology

Criteria	Mean*	SD
Using this technology would be useful in value addition of wheat flour	6.57	1.06
Using this technology will increase the market for quinoa	6.31	1.3
Using this technology would reduce quinoa losses	6.2	1.25
Using this technology would lead to increased use of quinoa in new food products	6.54	0.84
Using this technology would increase farmers' income	6.41	1.2
Learning to operate this technology would be easy for me	6.12	1.25

I would find the quinoa <i>mandazi</i> production technology easy to use	6.37	1.09
I have the intention to use this technology when it becomes available	6.48	1.11

*On a Likert scale of 1-7, where 1 = Extremely unlikely and 7 = Extremely likely

Word cloud for technology acceptance

The word cloud visually represents the frequency of words in text. Larger words appear more frequently indicating the main themes discussed, while smaller words appear less often. Some of the prominent words included in the word cloud (Figure 2.6.3);

- **Quinoa:** In addition to nutritional value, quinoa is a versatile crop (can be used in combination with many dishes) and has great sustainability in the sense that it can grow in harsh climatic conditions.
- **Technology:** There is a positive sentiment towards using technology, with statements like "I can try to use this technology" and "this technology is good." The technology is described as being easier to use and beneficial for health, as indicated by "it is easier and rich for our bodies." There was a suggestion that the technology could be improved, as seen in "the milling of quinoa should be done with more improvised mills to avoid losses."
- **Cost:** There were concerns about the high cost of quinoa. Too high cost of purchase is prohibitive making it difficult for people to afford. It was noted that making quinoa locally available and providing seeds at low cost could reduce the challenges related to ability to purchase the seeds.
- **Nutritious:** Emphasizing the nutritional value of quinoa. Quinoa was praised for its nutritional value (rich in minerals, vitamins, fiber and is considered complete protein), health benefits (can help with weight loss, important for children with malnutrition).
- **Milling: Milling of Quinoa:** The milling process for quinoa should be done with more improvised mills to avoid losses, to make more efficient, to make quinoa flour more affordable and accessible. From the stakeholders, the current milling methods may not be efficient and could

The results of economic analysis are shown in Table 2.6.4.

Table 2.6.4: Economic analysis results

PARAMETER	VALUE
Production cost per kg powder (US\$)	4.64
Selling price per kg powder (US\$)	5.57
Benefit-cost ratio	1.19
Return on Investment – ROI (%)	18.75
Profit margin (%)	15.79

The results of economic analysis in Table 2.6.4 show that investment in the milling plant is economically viable. However, the selling price is very high compared to that of other less nutritious cereals because of the high purchasing price of quinoa grains.

2.6.4.2 Relevant production

Poster on “New quinoa-based products for improving the nutritional status and dietary diversity of children (2-6 years) in Kitui county”, Agricultural Show, Kitui, 27 July, 2023.

Poster on “Quality of diets consumed by children aged 2-6 years in Kitui County”. Nairobi Innovation Week, University of Nairobi, 26 - 28 April, 2024.

2.6.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kitui (KE)	Quinoa mandazi snacks	40 farmers/ processors

2.6.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kitui Food Hub	Quinoa mandazi snacks	<p>Increase in nutrient intake by school children</p> <p>Technology acceptance 6.48 on a likert scale of 1-7 where 1 is extremely unlikely and 7 is extremely likely.</p> <p>A 18.75% Return-on-Investment</p>

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.6.5 Conclusions

The study established that a nutrient rich snack from quinoa-wheat composite flour (quinoa at 70%), can be prepared and used to improve dietary diversity of preschool children in Kenya.

The results of this study continue to be disseminated to different stakeholders, including county government officials, with a view of motivating them to promote the cultivation of quinoa to increase production and to lower the market price that is currently very high.

2.7. Therapeutic food (tamarillo juice, for adults with diabetes)

2.7.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

The tree tomato (*Solanum betaceum* Cav) is a small abandoned shrub tree with Andean origins that is cultivated for its edible juicy fruits. The fruits are high in minerals, vitamins, and bioactive compounds. Among the bioactive compounds contained in tree tomato are chlorogenic acids, which have significant diabetes-regulating properties (Viera et al., 2022). Given the fruit's high antioxidant properties, it has been found that regular consumption boosts consumers anticancer, antidiabetic, neuro and cardio protective effects among other benefits (Viera et al., 2022).

In Kenya, the most common varieties of tree tomatoes are red, although there are also white-fleshed varieties. However, there are few processing methods for the fruit, resulting in high post-harvest losses as the fruits are sold fresh in various major markets (Muriithi et al., 2013). Although the fruits are commonly consumed fresh in households, a processing plant has been established among farmer groups, which is currently processing value-added products such as jams, chutneys, and fruit yogurts (Nyawira, 2018) .

The current assignment sought to standardize the processing techniques for sugarless commercially viable tree tomato and mulberry leaf extracts ready to drink beverages based on the Kenyan standards for processed fruits drinks and the general food safety standards (KEBS, 2016) (KEBS, DKS 2580:2018) for the management of type II diabetes among diabetic patients in selected sites in Kenya. The therapeutic tree tomato is meant to aid with the management of type II diabetes among pre and diabetic patients which has been on the increase in the recent past.

Besides addressing the high post-harvest losses among tree tomato farmers who mainly depend on fresh market sales, value addition into ready to drink beverages will ensure consumer access to shelf- stable products long after the fruits are out of season. This will lead to socio-economic empowerment among households especially in the rural areas where the fruits grow, creation of both direct and indirect employment among processors and the youth.

A description of the research and innovation process carried out to develop quinoa enriched new food product, including the prerequisites, the participants and the results (based on impact pathway) follows.

2.7.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Technical components and infrastructure necessary to build the prototype, are provided below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	<i>Fruit washing trough (US\$ 388)</i>	M
2	<i>Fruit Destoner (US\$ 6,230)</i>	M
3	<i>Fruit pulper (US\$ 6,250)</i>	M
4	<i>Batch pasteurizer (US\$ 6,300)</i>	M
5	<i>Packaging machine (US\$ 39,063)</i>	M
6	<i>Land and building (US\$ 39,000)</i>	M
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.7.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Pulping of tree tomato fruits was carried out at the University of Nairobi and at the Kitui Enterprise Promotion Company Limited (KEPC) premises in Kitui Town, Kitui Food Hub using automated pulping machines. Operations involved during the pulping process included sorting, cleaning, sanitization, blanching, size reduction, pulping, sieving and homogenization of the pulp. Over 40 people who included local farmers and processors were able to learn about the new technology during the validation process, but only 37 responded to the technology assessment questionnaire that was administered. Tree tomato fruits were pulped then dried using the drier, milled into powder then packaged. Feedback on the process was collected from the respondents on the conducted activities, outputs reached, outcomes and impact of the innovative technology.

Sugarless ready-to-drink beverages were prepared with the incorporation of freshly squeezed lemon juice as a flavoring agent added at a rate of 2.5% for all

the formulations. The tamarillo nectars (40% and 30% fruit ratios) were prepared as per the KEBS fruit requirements of a minimum 25% fruit as standards for fruit nectars and filling to volume using potable water. Blended formulations of 20%:20% and 30%:10% of the fruit pulp and mulberry leaf extracts respectively were processed. The permitted preservatives sodium sorbate and sodium metabisulphite were added in synergistic ratios of 0.015% to preserve colour and prevent bacteria, yeast, and mold growth. All the formulations were pasteurized for 5-6 minutes at 85°C and hot filled at 45-55°C into food grade plastic bottles. Raw materials and developed products were characterized as per the methods in (D4.11).

The efficacy of the developed tree tomato juice was tested on diabetic and pre-diabetic participants in Mukurweini Food Hub. The Tamarillo study took place in Nyeri County which was purposively selected because of the high prevalence of diabetes. The study had a cross-sectional component, interventional where Tamarillo juice, Tamarillo:Mulberry blend and Water was randomized to the various Hospitals. Data collection involved using both ODK and computer for blood sugar analysis. This was done by trained Hospital staff from each hospital (2 Laboratory staff, 2 Nurses from the Diabetics clinics and 2 Nutritionists). Hba 1c test (blood sugar test) was administered to all participants once and repeated collection of random blood sugar per week by the Hospitals Laboratory staff. One hundred and twenty (120) study participants who were diabetic or pre-diabetic attending three hospitals, were randomly selected from: Nyeri hospitals, the Karatina Hospital and Mukurwe-ini hospital. At the onset of the study, data on social –demographic characteristics, nutritional status , physical activity of the participants were collected. The Hba 1c test was administered to all the 120 participants. The Random blood sugar was administered to the participants; however, they were given Tamarillo juice in Mukurweini hospital and then they were made to wait for 2 hours and the sugar level checked again. The same process was repeated for Nyeri hospital study participants but they were given Tamarillo:Mulberry blend juice and Karatina Hospital had the same treatment but Drinking bottled water (from University of Nairobi) was provided. Data collection for 2 subsequent weeks in Mukurweini Hospital but for only one subsequent week in both Karatina and Nyeri hospitals.

Validation of the process technology and the fruit juice was done at the KEPC processing plant in Kitui Food Hub. The tree tomato juice production technology was demonstrated to farmers and processors and 37 respondents completed a tree tomato juice production technology assessment questionnaire.

The R&I path was as follows:

- i. **Product formulation and development** based on the Kenya Bureau of Standards specifications.
- ii. **Product testing for safety and qualitative** tests based on standard chemical and microbiological testing processes.
- iii. **Consumer sensory testing** using sensory experimental setups.
- iv. **Product rework after the sensory testing** to integrate the consumer preferences.
- v. **Patient tests** (efficacy trials) at selected clinical setup sites in Mukurweini Food Hub.
- vi. **Validation of the technology** at the KEPC factory, Kitui Food Hub.

2.7.4 Summary of the outputs

2.7.4.1 Results and achievements

The process led to the development of acceptable shelf-stable plain and mulberry blended tree tomato products. Trials with actual patients led to stabilization of sugars among the prediabetic and diabetic patients in the study areas.

The colour parameters of the tree tomato nectars are shown in Table 2.7.1. The values of L* and b* for tamarillo and blended tamarillo nectars did not differ significantly ($p>0.05$). However, the blended tamarillo nectar had higher values.

Table 2.7.1: Colour parameters of the tree tomato nectars

Values are Mean±SD; Values with different superscripts in the same column are statistically

Samples	Color parameters			
	L*	a*	b*	Chroma*
Tamarillo nectar	37.03±0.53 ^a	9.18±2.41 ^a	2.83±0.17 _a	9.64±2.25 ^a
Blended tamarillo nectar	34.46±0.99 _a	10.81±2.11 ^b	3.43±0.37 _a	11.34±2.12 ^b
P value	0.175	0.004	0.350	0.026

different ($p \leq 0.05$). Tamarillo nectar: 40% tamarillo pulp concentration; Blended tamarillo nectar: 20% tamarillo pulp and 20% muuberry leaf extract concentration of both a* and Chroma*.

Table 2.7.2 shows the proximate composition of the tree tomato nectars. Tamarillo nectar (40% tamarillo pulp concentration in water) is significantly higher than the blended tamarillo nectar in moisture, protein and ash contents ($p \leq 0.05$). It is, however, lower in fibre, fat, carbohydrate and energy contents ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.7.2: Proximate composition of tree tomato nectars

Sample	Moisture (%)	Fibre	Ash (g)	Protein (g)	Fat (g)	Carbohydrates (g)	Energy Kcal/100 g
Tamarillo nectar	97.55±0.61 ^b	0.63±0.13 ^a	0.43±0.31 ^a	0.52±0.19 ^a	0.01±0.00 ^a	0.87±0.97 ^a	5.63±3.12 ^a
Blended tamarillo nectar	96.19±0.13 ^a	0.68±0.02 ^a	0.39±0.05 ^a	0.46±0.20 ^a	0.02±0.00 ^a	2.26±0.19 ^b	11.07±0.63 ^b
P value	0.005	0.446	0.805	0.681	0.56	0.030	0.014

Values are Mean±SD; Values with different superscripts in the same column are statistically different ($p \leq 0.05$). Tamarillo nectar: 40% tamarillo pulp concentration; Blended tamarillo nectar: 20% tamarillo pulp and 20% mulberry leaf extract concentration

The chemical and mineral compositions of tamarillo nectar and blended tamarillo nectar are shown in Table 2.7.3. The contents of Ca, Mg, Na, Mn, Zn and Fe are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$). The blended tamarillo nectar is higher in potassium and phosphorus than the tamarillo nectar ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table 2.7.3: Chemical and mineral compositions of the tree tomato nectars

Sample	Total soluble solids (f.w)	pH (f.w)	Chemical parameter (per 100 g dry.weight.)							
			Ca	Mg	K	Na	P	Mn	Zn	Fe
Tamarillo nectar	2.00±0.0 ^a	4.31±0.02 ^a	3.20±0.1 ^a ₂	5.04±0.6 ^a ₀	23.14±0.3 ^a ₀	0.23±0.0 ^a ₂	2.67±0.4 ^a ₄	0.03±0.00 ^a	0.03±0.0 ^a ₀	0.10±0.02 ^a
Blended tamarillo nectar	3.00±0.0 ^a	4.28±0.02 ^a	2.64±0.5 ^a ₄	5.51±0.3 ^a ₅	29.96±2.7 ^a ₂	0.28±0.0 ^a ₃	5.97±1.0 ^a ₀	0.02±0.00 ^a	0.03±0.0 ^a ₀	0.12±0.02 ^a
P value		0.175	0.089	0.226	0.002	0.062	0.001	0.090	0.169	0.166

Values are Mean±SD; Values with different superscripts in the same column are statistically different ($p \leq 0.05$). Tamarillo nectar: 40% tamarillo pulp concentration; Blended tamarillo nectar: 20% tamarillo pulp and 20% mulberry leaf extract concentration

Table 2.7.4 shows the phytochemical compositions of the tamarillo nectar and the blended tamarillo nectar. Tamarillo nectar is higher in Vitamin C and flavonoids than the blended tamarillo nectar. The two nectars are not significantly different in phenolics content and antioxidant activity.

Table 2.7.4: Phytochemical composition

Sample	Vitamin C (mg/100ml f.w))	Chemical parameter (per 100 g dry.weight.)		
		Phenolics (mg GAE d.w)	Flavonoids (mg.CE d,w)	Antioxidant activity (µMTE)
Tamarillo nectar	36.63±1.48 ^b	105.43±1.89 ^a	439.50±23.10 ^b	6915.25±412.89 ^a
Blended tamarillo nectar	21.92±0.99 ^a	104.85±1.75 ^a	330.75±6.18 ^a	7775.50±89.26 ^b
P value	0.001	0.671	<0.0001	0.007

Values are Mean±SD; Values with different superscripts in the same column are statistically different (p≤0.05). Tamarillo nectar: 40% tamarillo pulp concentration; Blended tamarillo nectar: 20% tamarillo pulp and 20% mulberry leaf extract concentration

Microbial quality of the two tamarillo nectars is shown in Table 2.7.5. While yeast and moulds and E. Coli were not detected, the TVC levels were lower than the maximum limit as per KS EAS 948.2019. The two nectars meet the microbiological quality requirements and are safe with regard to E. coli infection.

Table 2.7.5: Microbial quality of tree tomato nectars

Description	Microbial characterization of tree tomato nectars (cfu/ml)		
	TVC*	Yeast and Molds	E. Coli
Tamarillo nectars	5.31±0.56 ^a	Not detected	Not detected
Blended tamarillo nectar	4.5±2.07 ^a	Not detected	Not detected
P value	0.476		

Values (means± standard deviation) with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, P≤0.05).

* Maximum allowed – 10³ as per KEBS standards for Fruit juices and nectars Specification (KS EAS 948:2019).

Tamarillo nectar: 40% tamarillo pulp concentration; Blended tamarillo nectar: 20% tamarillo pulp and 20% mulberry leaf extract concentration

The sensory evaluation scores for the tree tomato and blended tree tomato extracts as well as other ready to drink beverages are shown in Table 2.7.6. The two juices are not significantly different in appearance, taste, mouthfeel and after taste ($p>0.05$).

Table 2.7.6: Sensory scores for the tree tomato, mulberry leaf extract and blended tree tomato ready to drink beverages

Formulations	Sensory parameters						Overall Acceptability
	Appearance	Odor	Taste	Texture	Mouthfeel	After taste	
40% Tree tomato	5.38 ^a	5.20 ^b	4.08 ^c	4.96 ^a	4.26 ^a	4.26 ^b	4.78 ^b
30% tree tomato	5.16 ^a	5.12 ^b	3.60 ^{bc}	4.40 ^a	4.0 ^a	4.16 ^b	4.20 ^{ab}
20% mulberry:20% tree tomato	5.06 ^a	4.76 ^{ab}	4.04 ^c	4.28 ^a	4.12 ^a	4.14 ^b	4.22 ^{ab}
30% fruit pulp: 10% leaf extract	4.72 ^a	4.72 ^{ab}	3.44 ^{bc}	4.26 ^a	3.86 ^a	3.76 ^{ab}	4.04 ^{ab}
50% Mulberry leaf extract	4.66 ^a	3.94 ^a	2.96 ^{ab}	4.44 ^a	3.38 ^a	3.28 ^{ab}	3.76 ^{ab}
75% Mulberry leaf extract	4.80 ^a	3.90 ^a	2.52 ^a	4.1 ^{4a}	3.36 ^a	2.72 ^a	3.34 ^a
P-value	0.359	0.001	<0.0001	0.277	0.106	0.000	0.006

Values (means± standard deviation) with different superscripts along a column are statistically different (Tukey's test, $P\leq 0.05$).

Efficacy of the tree tomato nectars on pre-diabetic and diabetic participants

Demographic characteristics of study participants

Few participants came from households where they were living alone (15%) (Table 2.7.7).

Table 2.7.7: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of study participants

	Number	Percent
Age of participant in years		
Below 30 yrs	1	1%
30-34 yrs	2	1%
35-55 yrs	63	35%
more than 55yrs old	115	64%
Years the person has the suffered from diabetes symptoms		
below 1 year	69	38%
1 year	35	19%
more than 2 years	77	43%
Gender of participants		
Female	139	77%
Male	42	23%
Marital status		
Married	118	65%
Widowed	36	20%
Single	15	8%
Separated	9	5%
Divorced	3	2%
Education level		
Completed primary	50	28%
Primary drop-out	39	22%
Completed Secondary	35	19%
Secondary drop-out	23	13%
College	11	6%
Never went to school	9	5%
In primary	7	4%
University	2	1%
In secondary	2	1%
Other (specify)	1	1%
Form 6	1	1%

	Number	Percent
Adult Education	1	1%
Occupation		
Farmer	109	60%
Businessperson	31	17%
Casual laborer	10	6%
Salaried employed	10	6%
Unemployed	5	3%
Other (specify)	4	2%
Religion		
Protestant	108	60%
Catholic	54	30%
Other (specify)	19	10%
Home ownership		
Self-owned	131	72%
Rented	23	13%
Hosted by parent for free	16	9%
Hosted by relative for free	2	1%
Hosted by friend for free	1	1%
Land ownership		
Yes	156	86%
No	25	14%
Type of Sanitation facility		
Flush toilet	55	30%
Pit latrine	157	87%
Free range	-	-
Main source of food		
Market	80	44%
own farm	69	38%
Kiosks/supermarket	30	17%
other farms	2	1%

Food consumption practices in relation to non-communicable diseases protect score and risk score

The study participants had a high global dietary recommendation (GDR) score of 13.45 (21.5) [mean(SD)]. Zero consumption of vegetable and fruits was at 1% and consumption of animal source foods was high (93%). Consumption of sweetened beverages was low 18% with tea taking the highest contributor and a low soft drink consumption (2%) was observed.

Consumption of food groups used for the computation of non-communicable diseases protect score

Consumption of the food groups used to compute NCD protect score was quite moderate to high, however, nut, seeds and citrus fruit were less consumed (Table 2.7.8). The mean (SD) NCD protect score -5.28(2.6).

Table 2.7.8: Consumption of food used for the classification of NCD protect score (24 hour recall)

	Yes	No
Whole grains	60%	40%
Pulses	77%	23%
Nuts and seeds	17%	83%
Vitamin A-rich orange vegetables	56%	44%
Dark green leafy vegetables	76%	24%
Other vegetables	83%	17%
Vitamin A-rich fruits	29%	71%
Citrus	36%	64%
Other fruits	61%	39%

Consumption of food groups used for the computation of non-communicable diseases risk score

Consumption of food groups linked with high risk towards communicable disease was very low (Table 2.6.8) except for unprocessed red meat (35%) and

deep fried foods (17%) which much higher compared to the other food groups (Table 2.7.9). The mean (SD) of NCD risk score was 0.83 (1.16).

Table 2.7.9: Consumption of food used for the classification of NCD risk score

	0	1
Soft drinks	98%	2%
Baked/grain-based sweets	91%	9%
Other sweets	96%	4%
Processed meat	94%	6%
Unprocessed red meat	65%	35%
Deep fried food	83%	17%
Fast food & Instant noodles	98%	2%
Packaged ultra-processed salty snacks	100%	0%

Consumption of fruit varieties among study participants

Fruits mainly consumed by pre-diabetic adults were oranges (59%), bananas (57%), thorn melon (35%), tree tomato (29%), papaya (20%), followed by apples, pineapples and passion fruits. The least consumed fruits were pepino, avocados, and mango most likely due to seasonality of the fruits (Table 2.7.10).

Table 2.7.10: Consumption of fruits among the study participants

	Number	Percent
Oranges	107	59%
Thorn melon	86	48%
water melon	63	35%
Bananas	104	57%
Pineapples	28	15%
papaya	37	20%
Tree tomato	52	29%
Apples	34	19%
Mango	11	6%
Passion fruit	30	17%

Pepino	5	3%
Avocado	5	3%
No fruits eaten	15	8%

Challenges, comorbidities, complications, infections experienced by participants

Nearly half of the study participants monitored their blood sugar levels. The most common symptoms of hyperglycemia were fatigue, troubled vision, hunger, frequent urination and thirst, each experience by more than a third of the group (Table 2.7.11). The main type of complication was reported to be effect on the eyes (27%) while blood pressure was the main co-morbidity (59%). The burning sensation while urinating, frequent colds/flu and itching groins or feet were mentioned to be the most common challenges experienced by the pre-diabetic adults.

Table 2.7.11: Challenges, comorbidities, complications, infections experienced by participants

	Number	Percent
Do you monitor your blood sugar		
No	103	57%
Yes	78	43%
Symptoms frequently experienced		
Fatigue	74	41%
Hunger	59	33%
Thirst	47	26%
Frequent desire to urinate	58	32%
trouble focusing vision	62	34%
Low Blood sugar	22	12%
Problems or infections encountered		
acne	6	3%
burning on urination	27	15%
frequent colds	19	10%
itching in the groin or feet	29	16%

boils	4	2%
Comorbidities		
high blood pressure	107	59%
gastritis	15	8%
Arthritis	26	14%
Cardiac condition	3	2%
None	55	30%
complications		
Kidney	3	2%
Eyes	49	27%
Cardiac condition	2	1%
None	130	72%

Nutritional status of study participants

Proportion of men who were overweight/obese (43%) was higher compared to that of women participants (19%) (Table 2.7.12) as per the waist hip ratio, however, BMI classification (67% vs 79% [men vs women]) showed the opposite, but no statistical difference between men and women.

Table 2.7.12: Waist hip ratio and body mass index of study participants

	Female n(%)	Male n(%)	Chi	p- value
Waist-hip ratio			9.6	0.02
Normal	112(81)	24(57)		
Overweight	27(19)	18(43)		
Body mass index			5.1	0.82
Underweight	2(1)	0(-)		
Normal	28(20)	14(33)		
Overweight	48(35)	16(38)		

Obese 61(44) 12(29)

Diabetes status based on HbA1C

Based on the (CDC¹ 2024), HbA1C is used to group (identify persons with diabetes or prediabetes according to the following cut off points; HbA1C below 5.7% normal, 5.7-6.4% pre-diabetic and $\geq 6.5\%$ diabetic. The diabetes (pre-diabetes) status of participants is shown in Table 2.7.13. There were no statistical differences in the diabetes status of participants for the intervention and comparison health facilities.

Table 2.7.13: Diabetes mellitus status of study participants based on the HbA1C blood test

	Normal N(%)	Prediabetic N(%)	Chi	p-value
Mukurweini	8(13)	54(87)	2.1	0.91
Nyeri referral hospital	3(5)	54(95)		
Karatina	5(11)	42(89)		

Impact of consumption of tree tomato juice on random blood sugar of pre-diabetic adults

Even though the blood sugar levels varied at the before intake of juice in one facility and the other facilities, the mean difference of before-after juice intake was statistically significant for the high juice concentration (40% tamarillo concentration) and the 30% tamarillo concentration or intake of plain water (Table 2.7.14). The 30% concentration was not statistically different from that of

¹ <https://www.cdc.gov/diabetes/diabetes-testing/prediabetes-a1c-test.html#:~:text=A1C%20results,Diabetes%3A%206.5%25%20or%20above>

plain water consumption even though the mean difference was numerically higher 1.62 ± 1.64 versus 1.37 ± 1.15 of plain water.

Table 2.7.14: Means and Standard deviations for Random blood sugar before and intervention and means of differences

Hosp		RBS1	RBS2	dRBS
Mukurweini	40% tamarillo fruit concentration	10.35 ± 4.09^b	8.05 ± 3.56^b	2.30 ± 1.54^b
Nyeri ref	30% tamarillo fruit concentration*	8.26 ± 3.28^a	6.64 ± 2.64^a	1.62 ± 1.64^a
Karatina	Zero Juice (Plain water)	8.26 ± 2.99^a	7.46 ± 3.24^{ab}	1.37 ± 1.15^a

Values are Mean \pm SD; Values with different superscripts in the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$)

* Also had 10% mulberry leaf extract

RBS1 – Random blood sugar before juice intake; RBS2- Random blood sugar after juice intake; dRBS – Reduction of RBS (RBS1-RBS2)

Economic feasibility

The economic feasibility of commercial production of tree tomato juice is shown in Table 2.7.16. Table 2.7.15 shows the investment costs

Table 2.7.15: Investment costs

ITEM	COST (US\$)
Fruit washing trough	388
Fruit pulper (Destoner)	6,250
Fruit pulper (Refiner)	6,250
Batch pasteurizer	6,300
Packaging machine	39,063
Land and building	39,000
TOTAL	97,639

The results of economic analysis are shown in Table 2.7.16.

Table 2.7.16: Economic analysis results

PARAMETER	VALUE
Production cost per kg juice (US\$)	0.94
Selling price per kg juice (US\$)	1.22
Benefit-Cost ratio	1.30
Return on Investment – ROI (%)	30.22
Profit margin (%)	23.20

The results of economic analysis in Table 2.7.16 show that investment in a tomato juice factory producing 300 tons of 40% fruit pulp tree tomato nectar is economically viable.

Technology acceptance

Validation of the tamarillo fruit juice technology was done at the Kenya Enterprise Promotion Company Limited (KEPC) factory premises located within the Kitui Food Hub. The tree tomato pulping and juice production was demonstrated to the local farmers and the factory personnel. A standard technology acceptance questionnaire was completed by 37 respondents and the results are shown in Table 2.7.17.

Table 2.7.17: Tree tomato nectar production technology acceptance

ACCEPTANCE PARAMETERS	LIKELY						UNLIKELY
	Extremely	Quite	Slightly	Neither	Slightly	Quite	Extremely
Using this technology would be useful in preserving	97.3	2.7	0	0	0	0	0

tree tomato fruit							
Using this technology will increase the market for tree tomato fruits	94.6	5.4	0	0	0	0	0
Using this technology would reduce tree tomato losses	94.6	5.4	0	0	0	0	0
Using this technology would reduce sugar intake by consumers	100	0	0	0	0	0	0
Using this technology would increase farmers' income	91.9	8.1	0	0	0	0	0
Learning to operate this technology would be easy for me	94.6	2.7	2.7	0	0	0	0
I would find the tree tomato juice production technology easy to use	91,9	5.4	2.7	0	0	0	0
I have the intention to use this	94.6	5.4	0	0	0	0	0

technology when it becomes available							
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All the technology acceptance parameters were reported to be “likely extremely” by 91.9-100 % respondents while the rest of the respondents who were not in this category reported that the technology acceptance parameters are “quit likely”. No respondent indicated that any of the technology acceptance parameters is slightly unlikely, quite unlikely or extremely unlikely.

2.7.4.2 Relevant production

Publication submitted to *LWT - Food Science and Technology* and is under review - Sensory characterization and instrumental analysis of the aromatic profile for the enhancement of African tamarillo (*Solanum betaceum* L.) fruit drink (De Tura et al., 2024).

2.7.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kitui (KE)	Tree tomato juice	37
Mukurweini (KE)	Tree tomato juice	120

2.7.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
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Kitui (KE)	Tamarillo juice production technology	A 30.2% Return-on-Investment (ROI)
		Over 94% of the respondents who participated in the validation exercise have the intention to use this technology when it becomes available.
Mukurweini (KE)	Tamarillo juice	Decrease in Random Blood Sugar after intake of 40% tamarillo juice is 1.68 times that after water intake.

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.7.5 Conclusions

The tree tomato resulted in a high potential anti-diabetic therapeutic drink that could be integrated as part of the diabetes management and suppression. It has a low glycemic index and its chlorogenic acid content helps in controlling glucose level in diabetic patients. Further evaluations among diabetics needs to be conducted at national levels while developing policy guidelines for integrating the fruits as part of diabetics' food. It is highly recommended that the innovation be adopted and scaled up to promote the commercialization of tree tomato nectars in Kenya.

References

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2.8. Prototype for bean sauce

2.8.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

In Eastern Africa and Uganda in particular, farmers have limited access to technologies to reduce post-harvest losses (qualitative and quantitative). Beans on the market are typically poor quality and prone to developing the ‘hard-to-cook (HTC) phenomena’, resulting in cooking times of 1-4 hours (Nyakuni et al., 2008; Balamaze et al., 2008). This makes bean preparation laborious, with high fuel requirements. Availability and use of value-added products with reduced cooking times is limited and consumers tire of the monotonous flavor of boiled beans, reducing their bean consumption despite documented high nutrient content and health benefits. Optimized processing (de-hulling, soaking, milling, fermentation, germination, and extrusion cooking) can enhance digestibility and nutritional value by reducing phytates and polyphenols that limit iron uptake, and create value-added bean-based products (Nkundabombi et al., 2015; Ndagire et al., 2015; Nakitto et al., 2015). The objective of the activities under this prototype was to develop a process for production of precooked bean sauce and evaluate the acceptance of the product.

A description of the research and innovation process carried out to develop bean source, including the prerequisites, the participants and the results (based on impact pathway) follows.

2.8.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for the implementation of the prototype are given below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Ingredients Iron- and zinc-rich dry beans	1
2	Milling equipment (grain mill)	1
3	Extruder	1
4	Weighing scales	1
5	Packing and sealing machines	1
6	Packaging materials	1

7	Personnel (e.g. researchers and production staff)	1
8	Finances (for raw materials, packages and staff costs)	1
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.8.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Selection of the bean variety for processing

NARO Bean 1, a breeder-certified dry bean variety in Uganda was selected for processing, because of its desirable characteristics including: early maturity of 60 to 68 days; high yield of 600 to 800 kg per acre; high zinc and iron contents and high sensory acceptability (MAAIF, 2024).

Raw material acquisition and pre-processing

The dry beans were delivered to Nutreal Limited by National Agricultural Agricultural Research Organisation (NARO) supported farmers in Rakai District. The beans were processed as described by Natabirwa et al. (2017), with modifications. Briefly, the beans were sifted and sorted on a wire mesh to remove chuff, broken and shrivelled grain. The sorted beans were washed thrice with potable tap water and dried on wire mesh racks in a solar tent drier, until they attained a moisture content of 11-12%. The dry beans were milled using a commercial mill (Model YZMF, Yize, Shuliy Henan, China) with a 1.5 mm sieve and the flour was stored in plastic bags at room temperature (23–27 °C).

Extrusion processing of the dry beans

The bean flour was extruded as described by Olamide et al. (2017). Briefly, the bean flour was conditioned to a moisture content of 20% and thoroughly mixed using a mixer for 15 min. The conditioned flour was then extruded using a DP70-III double screw inflating food machine (Jinan Eagle Machine Co. Ltd., Jinan, China). The extruder conditions were: feeding frequency of 30 Hz, cutting frequency of 50 Hz, and barrel temperatures of 60°C, 130°C, and 150°C in first, second, and third zones, respectively. After extrusion, the samples were cooled to room temperature under natural convection conditions. The samples were then milled into flour using a 30 B-C milling machine (Changzhou Erbang Drying

Equipment Co. Ltd., China), packed in 225 mm * 40 mic BOPP bags, a label was attached and the product was stored at ambient conditions until further use.

Developing a recipe for preparation of bean sauce using the extruded bean flour

Bean sauce was prepared using a recipe previously developed by Nutreal Limited and as described on the label. Briefly: 1 finely chopped large onion was sautéed in 2 tablespoons of cooking oil; 2 finely chopped tomatoes were added and cooked; 2 heaped table spoons of bean flour were added and stirred; 500 ml of hot water was added slowly while stirring; salt and seasonings were added to taste and the sauce was simmered for 10 minutes before serving.

Consumer testing/validation of bean sauce prepared using the bean flour

The recipe as well as the ingredients and fuel were provided to street vendors and they practiced preparing the bean sauce, in advance. A total of 302 street food vendors and their customers in Kampala District were interviewed after testing bean sauce. Street vendors were selected as the target users because they commonly serve cooked bean stew with *chapatti* (flat unleavened wheat-based product made by heating dough on oiled pan) to their clients. The stew is cooked using dry beans, which take 1-3 hours to cook, an inconvenient and costly process. The evaluation was conducted in the three busiest divisions of Kampala district namely: Kawempe (which includes the Kalerwe Food Hub of the Foodland project), Nakawa and Rubaga. A tool below was developed and translated into Luganda (the language commonly spoken language in central Uganda including Kampala), to ensure comprehension and used for data collection.

2.8.4 Summary of the outputs

2.8.4.1 Results and achievements

High sensory acceptability of the bean sauce prepared using the bean flour was established among a key target market segment. Overall the bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by the majority of respondents resulting in a combined like score of 85.8%. Only 9.2% neither liked nor disliked the product

and only 5% indicated that they did not like the product. The color of bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by a combined 94% the respondents. Only 5% of the respondents were undecided and only 1% said that they did not like the colour. Similarly, the aroma of bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by the respondents resulting in a combined like score of 91.1%. Only 5% of the respondents were undecided and only 4% indicated that they did not like the aroma of the product. The thickness of the bean sauce was liked by all the respondents. The taste of bean sauce was liked very much and moderately by the respondents resulting in a combined like score of 87.5%. Only 6.6% were undecided and only 6% indicated that they did not like the taste. The aftertaste of bean sauce was also liked very much and moderately by the respondents resulting in a combined like score of 90.7%. Only 5.6% were undecided and only 3.7% indicated that they did not like the aftertaste of the sauce. Detailed results are presented in D5.16.

2.8.4.2 Relevant production

No publication has resulted from this work.

2.8.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kamuli-Kalerwe (UG)	Bean sauce	302 street food vendors and their customers

2.8.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
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Kamuli-Kalerwe (UG)	Bean sauce	Continued production and promotion of the bean sauce flour among consumers in Uganda
Kamuli-Kalerwe (UG)	Bean sauce	The bean sauce flour is introduced for sale in at least 5 sales outlets in Kampala District by March 2025

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.8.5 Conclusions

A fast-cooking bean flour was refined and a highly acceptable bean sauce prepared from the flour was validated among a key target market segment in Kampala District. The high acceptability of the bean sauce in Kampala District is indicative of high acceptability country-wide because of the metropolitan nature of the population, representing the different cultures in Uganda. The bean sauce has potential to contribute to the nutrient (particularly protein, iron and zinc) intake of the target consumers.

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2.9. Wheat flour enriched with grain amaranth flour

2.9.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Foods such as *chapatti*, *mandazi*, doughnuts, *daddies* and cakes are commonly sold by road side food vendors and consumed by many low income earners and youths in Uganda. The foods are made using mostly imported and highly refined wheat flour. Locally grown grain amaranth (GA) (*Amaranthus cruentus*) is a suitable complement to wheat as it is locally grown, fast growing, draught resistant and nutritious. GA has 15% protein that is highly digestible and with a well-balanced amino acid profile as well as high levels of minerals and vitamins (Muyonga et al., 2008). The objective of the activities under this prototype was to develop a process for production of wheat-grain amaranth composite flour suitable for use in chapatti and evaluate the acceptance of the product.

A description of the research and innovation process carried out to develop wheat flour enriched with grain amaranth, including the prerequisites, the participants and the results (based on impact pathway) follows.

2.9.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for development of the prototypes are provided below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Food ingredients (wheat flour and amaranth grains)	1
2	Milling equipment (grain mill)	1
3	Packing and sealing machines	1
4	Packaging materials	1
5	Personnel (e.g. researchers and production staff)	1
6	Finances (for raw materials, packages and staff costs)	1

* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low

2.9.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

Brief description of the scientific-technological criteria and R&I path (development, test, and validation) for the realization of the new food products.

Raw material acquisition and pre-processing

Wheat flour was purchased from a large processor in Kampala – Uganda (who also fortifies the flours with micronutrients). Grain amaranth was delivered to Nutreal Limited by a lead Farmer of a farmers’ organisation in central Uganda. While the wheat flour was ready-to-use, the grain amaranth was pre-processed by sifting and sorting on a wire mesh to remove chuff, broken and shrivelled grain. The sorted grain was washed thrice with potable tap water and dried on wire mesh racks in a solar tent drier, until they attained a moisture content of 11–12%. The dry grains were milled using a commercial mill (Model YZMF, Yize, Shuliy Henan, China) with a 1.5 mm sieve and the flour was stored in plastic bags at room temperature (23–27 °C).

Refinement of the amaranth-wheat formulation

Previously developed formulations of GA-wheat composite flour were further refined and evaluated for use in chapatti, a food that is commonly prepared and sold by street food vendors in Uganda. Composites with 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60% and 70% GA flour were formulated and their nutritional composition was calculated based on existing nutrient data. The flours were then used for making *chapattis* (savory flat breads). The *chapatti* were screened by 9 experienced evaluators (6 males and 3 females), for their sensory acceptability.

Evaluation of the amaranth-wheat flour by street food vendors and their customers in Kampala – Uganda

The most acceptable composite was then evaluated among 302 street food vendors and their customers, concerning its potential for sale and use alongside and/or instead of pure wheat. Specifically, the street vendors evaluated the flour for ease of use and sensory acceptability of *chapattis* (flat breads) made using the flour. A 5-point hedonic scale was used by both the vendors and their customers.

2.9.4 Summary of the outputs

2.9.4.1 Results and achievements

Chapatti made with amaranth-wheat flour had higher sensory acceptability than those made from pure wheat. The former were liked very much by majority of the respondents (62.9%) while the later were liked moderately by the majority of consumers. The most preferred attributes for amaranth-wheat *chapattis* were thickness (86.9%), color (70%) and taste (65.2%) while for the *chapatti* made with pure wheat were color (60.1%) and aroma (55.9%). Majority (58.1%) of the consumers liked the *chapatti* made with pure wheat moderately whereas only (25.6%) liked it very much. Detailed results are presented in the report for D 5.16.

2.9.4.2 Relevant production

No publication has resulted from this work.

2.9.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Kamuli-Kalerwe (UG)	Wheat flour enriched with grain amaranth flour	302 street food vendors and their customers

2.9.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kamuli-Kalerwe (UG)	Wheat flour enriched with grain amaranth flour	Continued production and promotion of amaranth-wheat flour among consumers in Uganda

		Wheat-amaranth flour introduced for sale in at least 5 sales outlets in Kampala District by March 2025
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The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.9.5 Conclusions

An amaranth-wheat composite flour was refined and highly acceptable *chapatti* prepared from the flour was validated among a key target market segment in Kampala District. The high acceptability of the amaranth-enriched *chapattis* in Kampala District implies high acceptability country-wide because of the metropolitan nature of the population, representing the different cultures in Uganda. The amaranth-wheat flour has potential to contribute to the nutrient (particularly protein) intake of the target consumers, especially when consumed along with the bean sauce.

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2.10. Noodles from orange fleshed sweet potatoes and bio-fortified beans (partially substituting wheat)

2.10.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Many of the convenient processed foods, like noodles, available in Uganda are low in nutritional value and do not address the nutritional problems of under-nutrition, micro-nutrient deficiency and obesity, which are widely spread in the country (as reported in D2.5). Biofortified crops are specially bred to supply micronutrients of public health concern. Orange fleshed sweet potatoes are good sources of beta-carotene, a precursor for vitamin A. Biofortified beans, on the other hand are good sources of iron, zinc as well as proteins. Production of these two biofortified crops has been widely promoted in Uganda. Dietary intake of these biofortified crops has however remained limited, partly because they are not available in diverse forms.

The objectives of the research on noodles containing orange fleshed sweet potato and biofortified beans were to: i) Produce and pilot nutrient enriched noodles that have potential to address nutritional gaps; ii) Determine the nutritional and physico-chemical properties of the noodles produced.

A description of the research and innovation process carried out to develop noodles with OFSP, biofortified beans and grain amaranth partially substituting wheat, including the prerequisites, the participants and the results (based on impact pathway) follows.

2.10.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for the development of the prototype are outlined below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Availability of appropriate processing equipment and facilities	M
2	Processing skills development for SME staff	M

3	Availability of quality raw materials in sufficient volumes	M
4	Connection to electricity and water supply	1
5	Products certification	M
6	Access to suitable packaging materials and equipment	1
7	Storage facilities necessary to store raw materials and finished goods under suitable conditions.	1
8	Transportation and logistics: Vehicles and supply chain networks for sourcing raw materials and distributing finished products.	2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.10.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

The technological research undertaken to develop the optimal formulation and process for production of noodles containing OFSP and biofortified beans is detailed in D 4.12. Briefly, the process entailed optimisation by use of RSM.

The schematic below (Figure 2.10.1) shows the process developed for production of noodles from OFSP, biofortified beans and wheat.

Figure 2.10.1: Recommended process for production of noodles with wheat partially substituted with orange-fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans

The optimal substitution level for wheat was found to be 27%. Optimal processing conditions included dough thickness of 2 mm, drying time of 143.4 minutes and drying temperature of 80°C.

Noodles produced using the optimised process were analysed to determine their nutrient content, sensory and functional properties.

2.10.4 Summary of the outputs

2.10.4.1 Results and achievements

Noodles produced using the optimal formulation and process had significantly higher beta-carotene, fibre and protein content than noodles made based only on wheat (Table 2.10.1) and did not differ in sensory properties. Detailed results are reported in D5.16.

Table 2.10.1 Proximate analysis for the orange fleshed sweet potato and biofortified beans containing noodles

Sample	% Composition						
	Moisture	As h	Dietary fibre	Fat	Protein	Carbohydrates*	β-carotene (mg/100g)
Control	5.90 ^a ± 0.11	0.5 ^a ± 0.1	0.52 ^a ± 0.010	0.49 ^a ± 0.02	14.2 ^a ± 1.42	69.85	0.04 ^a ± 0.23 ¹
Nutrient enhanced noodles	5.98 ^a ± 0.07	2.1 ^b ± 0.1	11.77 ^b ± 0.67	0.61 ^a ± 0.08	35.06 ^b ± 0.39	44.48	0.54 ^b ± 0.01 ¹

Values are means \pm standard deviation of at least three determinations ($n=3$). Means in a column with different superscript are statistically different ($p \leq 0.05$). *Derived by difference.

2.10.4.2 Relevant production

Exploring new ingredients for nutritional enhancement of processed foods. Oral presentation at the 2024 International Journal Forum on Interdisciplinary Food Science (Food Bioscience & Food Nutrition) joint with the 16th ISNFF Conference and Exhibition. December 2024. Wuxi, China.

Natocho, J., Mugabi, R. and Muyonga, J.H., 2024. Optimization of formulation and processing conditions for the production of functional noodles containing orange-fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans. *Food Science & Nutrition*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fsn3.4167>

Natocho, J.O., Asiimwe, A., Mugabi, R. and Muyonga, J., 2023. Nutritional and Techno-Functional Properties of Noodles with Orange Fleshed Sweet Potatoes and Bio-fortified Beans. *Asian Journal of Food Science*. 23: 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.9734/afsj/2024/v23i9739>

Natocho, J.O., 2023. Utilization of orange fleshed sweet potato and bio-fortified beans for the production of nutritionally enhanced noodles (Masters thesis, Makerere University).

Natocho, J., Muyonga, J.H. & Mugabi, R. Utilization of orange fleshed sweet potatoes in production of noodles. Presentation made at the NARO-MAK conference held in Kampala, Uganda in March, 2023.

Natocho, J., Muyonga, J.H. & Mugabi, R. Utilization of orange fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans for production of nutritionally enhanced noodles. Presentation made at the 5th Federation of Africa Nutrition Societies Congress held in November 2023, in Dakar, Senegal.

2.10.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
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Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Nutrient enhanced noodles containing orange-fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans	1 SME
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2.10.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Kamuli/Kalerwe (UG)	Nutrient enhanced noodles containing orange-fleshed sweet potatoes and biofortified beans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Enhanced SME capacity in value addition ● Business opportunity for SME ● Improved access of consumers to nutrient rich products ● Increased farmer access to market for agricultural produce

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.10.5 Conclusions

Technological research, pilot testing and validation shows that developed noodles containing OFSP and biofortified beans are nutritious and highly acceptable. If widely applied, these noodles can contribute to improved nutrition in Uganda and beyond. Successful commercial implementation of the developed prototype, however, requires food processing enterprises to invest in noodles production and marketing. Products certification is another prerequisite for commercial exploitation of the developed noodles and this requires action by processing businesses and food certification bodies in respective project countries.

2.11. Fish oil

2.11.1 Prototype background, motivations and objectives

Barbus altianalis (rippon babel) is a native carp locally known as *Kisinjja* in Uganda. It is regarded as a high value species because it is cherished as culturally socially and economically important by communities in central and western regions of the country. The fish is also liked for its fatty soup. Currently, there is hardly any value addition to this species. The objective of the work on this species was to extract and characterise oil from the fish, with a view of determining the potential for using the fish as a source of oil with health benefits.

2.11.2 Prerequisites for the prototype

Prerequisites for the development of the prototype are outlined below.

Ref.	Requirement description	Priority*
1	Raw materials: Quality fish offal from GHP (Good Hygienic Practices) processing, Proximity to raw material source – e.g. fish processing facility	1
2	Equipment: Oil press	1
2	Others: Potable water, knives	1 - 2
* Priority: M = mandatory / 1 = high, 2 = medium, 3 = low		

2.11.3 Summary of the R&I activities: from testing to validating

In the study and validation activities samples were picked twice from a landing site at the Forest beach at the river Nile and from one farm in central Uganda. Few farms with *B. altianalis* have fish with quite a lot of fat for processing because the fish of less than a kilo does not have much fat. Fish picked from the wild had more fat for processing. The fat was largely obtained from the viscera of the fish. At the landing sites most of the viscera where the most fat is attached, is obtained from the fish that is landed and has had the viscera removed ready for transportation to the market. The fatty viscera is largely the fish that is starting the breeding stages where eggs require a lot of fat to build the eggs with

vitellogenesis (developing gonadal stages). Fish oil was extracted using an oil press machine. Laboratory analysis was then conducted to determine the physical and chemical properties of the sample, including specific gravity, refractive index, viscosity, melting point and oil stability.

2.11.4 Summary of the outputs

2.101.4.1 Results and achievements

The oil yield from visceral fat was 50%. The specific gravity of the sample averages at 0.9207, indicating the relative density compared to water. The values are consistent across the samples, with minimal variation, which is typical for uniform oil samples (De Silva et al., 2011). The refractive index of the sample averaged at 1.4873, which is within the expected range for fish oils, indicating the purity and quality of the sample (De Silva et al., 2011). The average viscosity is 20.67 cP. This value is typical for fish oil reflecting its resistance to flow at a specified temperature (Jeyakumari et al., 2015),. The melting point is consistently measured at -5°C across all samples, which is characteristic of fish oil. This consistency indicates that the samples are stable and have a similar fatty acid composition.

Table 2.11.1. Chemical attributes of oil made from *Barbus altianalis*

Chemical Parameter	Results during experimentation	Results during validation	Codex Standard (CXS 329-2017)
Acid Value (mg KOH/g)	10.367	11	≤ 3 mg KOH/g
Anisidine Value (% mass/mass)	12.177	15	≤ 20 % mass/mass
Iodine Value (I ₂ /100g)	90.403	82.6	Not specified

Chemical Parameter	Results during experimentation	Results during validation	Codex Standard (CXS 329-2017)
Moisture Content (% mass/mass)	5.500	4.6	Not specified
Peroxide Value (meq/kg)	14.533	7.6	≤ 5 meq/kg
Saponifiable Matter (mg KOH/g)	180.833	178.902	Not specified
Unsaponifiable Matter (% mass/mass)	11.283	8.6	Not specified

The results were compared against the Codex Alimentarius standard for fish oil (CXS 329-2017), which outlines acceptable limits for key quality indicators such as acid value, peroxide value, and anisidine value. The anisidine value was within the acceptable range, indicating that secondary oxidation products (aldehydes) are within acceptable limits. This suggests that the oil has not undergone extensive secondary oxidation, which is a positive sign regarding its freshness and stability. The results for acid value and peroxide value were, however, higher than acceptable limits. These are indicative of lipolysis and peroxidation and show a need for antioxidants and/ or better handling of the raw materials or the oil.

2.11.4.2 Relevant production

There have so far been no publication from this work.

2.11.4.3 Summary of the outcomes

Number of food operators involved in the validation activities (WP5).

Food Hub	Innovation (new food raw material / ingredient / food product)	n. farmers / SMEs
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Fish oil from <i>Barbus sp.</i>	30 farmers/2 SMEs

2.11.4.4 Summary of the impacts

Relevant key performance indicators (KPIs: technology, production, nutrition): measures

Food Hub	Innovation (new food product)	KPIs measuring the achievements
Masaka/Kajjansi (UG)	Fish oil from <i>Barbus sp.</i>	Fish oil with oxidative stability

The full set of functional and nutritional properties (NPIs) is reported in D5.16 (Report on the functional and nutritional properties of the validated FoodLAND new food products).

2.11.5 Conclusions

The analyses conducted (based on Codex standard scale), indicated that the oils were relatively stable. While fatty acids profile for the extracted oil was not determined, fish oils generally contain high levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), including omega 3 fatty acids, which have many health benefits, including prevention of non-communicable diseases. PUFAs also support brain growth, help stimulate skin and hair growth, maintain bone health, regulate metabolism, and maintain the reproductive system. Hence processing the oils is a critical path to ensure access to useful fatty acids cheaply for Uganda's population, especially those at highest risk of malnutrition and diseases like children, women and the elderly.

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3. Overall conclusion

A diversity of food products have been developed, many of which are rich in nutrients and bioactives, convenient and highly acceptable. Technological processes for production of the variety of products have been developed and tested at lab and pilot scale and results generally show high potential for these products to be accepted. Adoption of new technologies, however, requires sustained effort by multiple stakeholders. It is therefore important that engagement about the developed prototypes, with key stakeholders like local and national governments, non-governmental agencies and private sector continues. The formed Food Hubs should develop programs for continued engagement about the prototypes even beyond the FoodLAND project life. The Food Hubs should, among other actions, share information about the potential of the prototypes to address the nutritional, health and economic challenges faced by different population segments, especially vulnerable groups. Project private sector and NGOs can make important contributions towards scaling up and commercialisation of the developed prototypes

